

Industrialized deep renovation outlook

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Executive summary

This Outlook gathers the collective knowledge developed through the H2020 INFINITE project and the broader European community, mainly including the Energiesprong movement, to provide a comprehensive picture of where Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) stands today in Europe: what it is, why it is needed, how it is being practised, and what it will take to bring it to scale.

The urgency of renovation in Europe

Europe's building stock is at the heart of the continent's greatest environmental, social, and economic challenge. With **119 million residential buildings**, 40% of which were built before 1970 and 35% carrying the lowest energy performance ratings, the construction sector remains the largest energy consumer on the continent, accounting for around **28% of total final energy demand**. Space heating alone drives more than 60% residential energy use, relying heavily on fossil fuels. Despite binding commitmen-

ts from the Paris Agreement to the European Green Deal and its Renovation Wave Strategy, the current deep **renovation rate stands at a mere 0.2% per year** — a fraction of the 3% needed to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The consequences extend well beyond carbon: 9.3% of European citizens cannot afford to heat their homes adequately, and the construction sector itself struggles with aging workforces, low productivity, and a fragmented supply chain not yet suited to the transformation ahead.

The need for a new approach: Industrialized Deep Renovation

Against this backdrop, Industrialized **Deep Renovation** (IDR) has emerged as a necessary paradigm shift. Deep renovation — defined as achieving at least 75% reduction in primary energy consumption relative to the pre-retrofit baseline, bringing buildings **below 60 kWh/m²/year** — is the only class of intervention capable of genuinely decarbonizing the existing building stock. **Industrialization** takes this further: by shifting the **production of retrofit components** from individual job sites into **controlled factory environments**, IDR dramatically reduces on-site time, improves quality, lowers lifecycle costs, and enables the economies of scale without which deep renovation cannot become a mass-market practice.

Industrialized renovation is a subset of **Modern Methods of Construction (MMC)**, a broader family of approaches encompassing offsite pre-manufacturing, near-site assembly, onsite process improvements, and digital technology applications needed to increase the productivity and efficiency of the

sector. Within this family, IDR specifically leverages prefabricated façade panels, integrated rooftop modules, and smart building systems — designed and coordinated through BIM platforms and Design for Manufacture and Assembly (DfMA) principles — to deliver whole-building performance upgrades faster, more safely, and with greater certainty than any traditional approach.

The **benefits of IDR are layered**: direct advantages include shorter retrofit durations, higher manufacturing precision, lower disruption for occupants, and improved air quality and comfort. Indirect benefits extend across the building lifecycle from lower energy bills, and reduced maintenance costs, to increased asset value, better insurance terms, and significantly reduced carbon emissions. In addition, when IDR is implemented at scale across pipelines of similar buildings, economies of scale further compress costs, progressively making the approach economically self-sustaining.

Best practices: Energiesprong and European funded projects

The most proven and widely replicated IDR model to date is **Energiesprong**, born in the **Netherlands** and now active across France, Germany, the United Kingdom, and Italy. The movement demonstrates that a net-zero energy retrofit can be delivered at industrial scale with guaranteed long-term performance. More than **20.000 interventions across Europe** have consistently achieved over 50% reductions in energy consumption, up to 30% cost reductions compared to traditional approaches, and carbon footprint decreases of more than 75%. Each national adaptation of Energiesprong reflects local regulatory, financial, and market conditions: **France** has advanced furthest through the MASH purchasing consortium and large-scale social housing programs; **Germany** is benefitting from strong public investment and rapid industrialization with 17,000 retrofitted or under contract units driving 30–35% cost reductions; the **UK** has focused on collaborative procurement and alliance contracts to move from the current fragmented and highly linear process towards an ite-

relative, systemic approach focused on retrofit performances to be achieved; and **Italy** is building its supply chain through more than 1000 units renovated and a growing network of 30 construction companies and 15 social housing organizations.

Alongside Energiesprong, a wide landscape of **EU-funded research projects** — spanning Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, LIFE and Interreg programmes — has accelerated the development of IDR from different angles, with the majority favouring prefabricated panel solutions (60% of projects) and frequently combining them with photovoltaics, smart building systems, BIM-enabled design workflows, and innovative business and financing models. Among these, the **H2020 INFINITE** project stands out for its focus on flexible, kit-based retrofit solutions and for developing three demand-matched business models tailored to private condominiums, public social housing providers, and real estate developers and investors.

Case studies and technological trends

The 26 case studies collected across Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Spain, and the United Kingdom illustrate the diversity and growing maturity of IDR implementation in practice. Buildings ranging from 1950s terraced houses to 12-storey social housing towers have been successfully renovated using industrialized offsite façade panels combined with integrated renewable energy systems, smart controls, and performance guarantees of up to 30 years.

A trend analysis of **74 offsite retrofit solutions** reveals a market in vigorous early development. **Timber-frame panels** dominate with **68% of the dataset**, reflecting the strong tradition of timber construction in leading markets like Germany and France. 47% of solutions have already been applied to real projects, of which 30% are considered market competitive. Timber solutions tend to yield larger, **heavier** panels

(around 70 kg/m²) **installed faster on site** (180 m²/day on average), while light steel frame solutions offer lighter, more flexible modules suited to complex building geometries. **Italy** stands out for its **breadth of technological experimentation** — covering timber, steel, concrete, sandwich panels, and straw-based solutions — reflecting both the diversity of its building stock and the particular importance of seismic performance.

The overarching conclusion is clear: **offsite façade systems have the technical and economic potential to become the backbone of Europe's renovation acceleration**. The transition from promising innovation to mainstream practice requires continued R&D, maturing value chains, supportive regulation, and the right business models to mobilize private and public investment at the necessary scale.

About the project

Off-site prefabrication of multifunctional envelopes has been shown to be a technically viable approach to increase rate and quality of deep renovation of residential buildings. However, several barriers are still preventing a massive adoption of prefabricated solutions.

INFINITE aims at boosting the building renovation sector through the so-called “**Renovation4.0**” approach, which leverages on both digitalisation and industrialisation to offer **tailor-made solutions** with a high level of **design freedom, decrease retrofit costs and time** thanks to the optimisation of the value-chain and **foster the adoption of eco-compatible long-lasting products and systems**.

To do so, the INFINITE Project relies on three main pillars:

1. cross-fertilisation from digitization trends in other markets (i.e. Industry4.0);
2. exploitation of industrial capabilities and coupling with LC-thinking approach;
3. experience gained from the 1st generation of multifunctional prefabricated envelopes.

INFINITE promotes a life cycle approach that allows for comprehensive design, optimisation of the O&M and depletion of end-of-life residual value.

INFINITE partners cover the whole renovation value-chain. Together, they will develop a new generation of residential building renovation products and actions centred on the all-in-one industrialised Life-Cycle-based approach. Expected outputs include:

- a set of multi-user and multidisciplinary design tools;
- process-optimised all-in-one industrialised eco envelope kits, tested on **two** different residential and social buildings in **Italy** and **Slovenia**;
- **adaptive control systems**;
- set of **demand- and industry-side matched business models** to show the Renovation4.0 market potential;

- a **structured framework of entities and knowledge** able to clearly and widely demonstrate the Renovation4.0 benefits.

INFINITE will unleash the potential of the renovation industry by increasing the market penetration of sustainable, high-quality and long-lasting building retrofitting products and methods. This will ultimately contribute to the decarbonisation of the European building stock.

Entering more into details of the **five all-in-one industrialized envelope kits**, they consist of **modular timber frames** that can be easily installed on a building’s exterior to enhance energy efficiency and indoor comfort while reducing renovation time and costs. Each module **can include various technological components** contributing to meet Zero Energy Building (ZEB) targets, such as:

- Passive eco-friendly and green envelope solutions
- Energy and fresh air distribution systems
- Smart windows (smart glazing)
- Building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) systems
- Solar-thermal generation systems (BIST)

The design process is simplified by a **multi-user BIM platform** with plugins for LCA/LCC, energy and comfort, and O&M. This framework improves coordination among stakeholders and boosts the building’s environmental and economic performance.

A **building management system (BMS)** will ensure high performance over the building’s lifetime, providing performance information and serving as the central brain for the energy system, tailored to different users at both single flat and building levels.

1A PASSIVE ECO-COMPATIBLE & GREEN ENVELOPE KIT

The INFINITE industrialized green envelope kit optimizes the manufacturing and installation of façade elements with green cladding. It includes modules for both the building façade and roof, the latter coupled with a PV system. Additional components like a grey water treatment unit and a bio-electrochemical system (BES) enhance irrigation management, reducing operational and maintenance efforts. The grey water unit recirculates rainwater, while the BES generates electricity from wastewater treatment, powering environmental sensors.

2 ENERGY AND FRESH AIR DISTRIBUTION KIT

This façade kit provides fresh air, heating, and cooling thanks to the integration into the façade module. It includes a new Mechanical Ventilation Unit (MVU) with heat recovery and heat exchanged, air ducts, water pipes (to be connected to a centralised heat pump), electric wires, and a sensing and control unit. The system regulates fresh air and energy distribution (air-based) automatically depending on indoor conditions and comfort target levels.

3 SMART WINDOW KIT (SMART GLAZING)

The smart window kit features easy-to-install adaptive glazing solutions in a smart frame, pre-installed within the wooden façade module. Options include:

- Insulated glazing with wireless sensors for dynamic sun blind control.
- Dual band electrochromic glass (plasmochromic glass) for selective solar radiation regulation.

Both options include sensors for optical, thermal, and humidity data, powered by an integrated PV module, and are controlled by a smart system for optimal energy use and comfort.

4A ENERGY GENERATION BIPV KIT

INFINITE offers a customizable “plug & play” PV system designed to maximize energy harvesting and on-site renewable energy usage. Unlike classic solar panels, INFINITE PV panels are available in a wide range of colors and 3D textures. These panels are installed on a prefabricated wooden structure that can be placed on the façade or roof of the building. Once on-site, they only need to be fixed to the prefabricated module and plugged in, as the wooden frame already includes the supporting structure, reducing installation time and costs. The PV envelope is connected to centralized energy management hardware and software that optimize the flow between the BIPV system, energy storage, and the grid, allowing the building to meet nZEB standards.

4B

5 SOLAR-THERMAL GENERATION KIT (BIST)

The INFINITE Building Integrated Solar Thermal (BIST) system consists of industrialized envelope modules containing a solar thermal collector that generates energy from solar radiation. The system is connected to a centralized heat pump and two water tanks to produce heating and domestic hot water. This solution can also act as a cooling system, where the panels are used as evaporators. The BIST system is ideal for nZEB construction projects and highly energy-efficient renovation projects. The kit includes an adaptive controller with predictive modules and mixed physics and data-based learning models to ensure optimal performance with minimal energy use.

aBMS ADAPTABLE BMS (aBMS)

The INFINITE renovation concept considers human-building interaction to optimize energy use and achieve near ZEB standards during operation. A distributed network of sensors integrated at dwelling and building levels, as well as in all envelope components and kits, will be connected to a Building Management System (BMS) to communicate real-time data about comfort and energy needs. This allows users to control active systems according to provided suggestions. The aBMS, with predictive modules for weather and energy usage, evaluates the best control strategies for active devices, promoting self-consumption of locally generated electricity to ensure high internal comfort with minimal energy consumption. The aBMS offers services such as customizable alerts, predictive maintenance tools, and live data visualization on comfort and energy consumption. An intelligent thermostat allows dwellers to predict their annual energy bills based on their comfort preferences. The system adapts to different user types, including facility managers, maintenance operators, and dwellers.

BIM BIM PLATFORM (BIM)

The INFINITE BIM platform provides a smart design environment for data exchange, essential for industrialized renovation where precise design processes are fundamental. The platform offers a decision-support tool to help users select industrialized solutions, increasing production efficiency and improving envelope and building performance. It is an adaptable and fully interoperable Common Data Environment (CDE) with dedicated interfaces and capabilities, enabling data exchange with connected tools for better coordination among users and process phases. The INFINITE BIM platform includes the following plugins:

- LCC and LCA plugin – to optimize resources along the product life cycle, reduce negative impacts and risks, and maximize positive effects.
- Energy and comfort performance plugin – to provide designers with an optimized configuration of the all-in envelope kit, considering the interaction between energy demand, production from available renewable energy sources, and occupant comfort.
- Installation, O&M plugin – to assist installers, facility managers, and practitioners in operating correctly and timely during installation and O&M phases.

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1.

**The need for
a new
approach
in renovation**

KEY TAKEAWAYS BOX

- Europe's building stock is the continent's largest energy consumer (~28% of total final energy demand), with 40% of buildings pre-dating modern energy codes and 35% carrying the worst energy performance ratings.
- Space heating accounts for over 60% of residential energy use and still relies heavily on natural gas; decarbonizing this end-use is central to meeting climate targets.
- Despite the Paris Agreement, the European Green Deal, the Renovation Wave Strategy, EPBD, EED, and RED directives establishing increasingly stringent goals, actual deep renovation rates stand at just 0.2% per year — against a required rate of 3%.
- Energy poverty affects at least 9.3% of EU citizens who cannot adequately heat their homes, a figure that worsened significantly with the 2022 energy crisis.
- The construction sector faces structural weaknesses: an aging workforce, fragmented supply chains, low digitalization, and productivity below the EU economy average — all of which constrain the sector's capacity to accelerate renovation at the required scale.
- A triple strategy is needed: reducing energy demand through efficiency, decarbonizing energy supply through renewables, and addressing embodied carbon through low-carbon materials and lifecycle thinking.

1.1 EU goals and laws

Introduction

Due to high levels of consumption and emissions, there are many declarations of intent that demonstrate the effort that the world, the European Union, and individual countries are putting into setting clear and increasingly stringent targets and regulations.

To lay the foundations for a global commitment, during the COP 21 held in Paris on **12 December 2015**, the first legally binding international treaty on climate change, called **The Paris Agreement** (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change UNFCCC, 2016), was adopted by the European Union, together with 195 other parties.

To reach its objective of keeping the global temperature increa-

se to 1.5°C and below 2°C, the signing parties had to submit comprehensive national climate action plans (called National Determined Contributions - NDCs).

Since 2015, the number of countries mentioning actions to tackle building-related emissions in their NDC increased from 90 to 136. Also building energy codes (regulatory instruments that specify minimum energy efficiency standards for the residential and commercial stocks) raised from 60 to 80 and investments in energy efficiency continued to climb (+40%), mainly coming from a small number of European countries. However,

the challenges are still considerable since, if the effect of the pandemic is excluded, the decarbonization level reached in 2020 is only the 40% of the reference value needed to achieve the Paris Agreement goals (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021).

A triple strategy must be adopted to drastically lower buildings emissions:

- reducing energy demand, through energy efficiency measures and behavioural changes; decarbonizing the power supply, through electrification and use of renewable sources;
- addressing embodied carbon stored in building materials, through the use of low-carbon solutions.

In this direction, maximizing the refurbishment of existing buildings using a sustainable and whole life-cycle approach should be a key objective of upcoming policies and incentives.

With this in mind, the European Union has enacted several measures that direct and concretize the efforts aimed at achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement. Some of these measures are described in detail on the following pages and allocated funds are dealt with in XX .

European Green Deal

In 2019, the European Commission unveiled a set of policy initiatives with the goal of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels.

The objectives extend to many different sectors, including construction, since buildings accounted for 36% of global energy demand and 37% of energy-related CO₂ emissions in 2020¹.

With regard to this sector, the Green Deal focuses attention on new construction and redevelopment interventions and specifically addresses their unsustainable methods, which involve the use of many nonrenewable resources.

Therefore, the plan promotes the use of energy-efficient construction methods such as the design of “**climate-proof**” buildings. It also provides for increased **digitalization** and the implementation of rules related to the energy performance of buildings. Another issue addressed is the renovation of **social housing** buildings: it defines interventions aimed

at reducing the price of energy bills for those who have the most difficulty in meeting these costs². In addition, it is intended to triple the renovation rate of all buildings in order to reduce the pollution emitted during their operational lifecycle³.

As a consequence of the increasing environmental crisis, climate neutrality is one of the most relevant and challenging goals of the whole European Union:

Reaching an economy with net-zero⁴ greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 is at the heart of the European Green Deal in line with the EU’s commitment to action expressed in the Paris Agreement.

In this field, several goals, laws and funds have been issued by the European Union as chronologically summarized below.

The first climate-neutral continent

by 2050

At least 55% less

net greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, compared to 1990 levels

3 billion

additional trees to be planted in the EU by 2030

Source: official website of the European Commission

¹ 2021 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction.

² Building and renovating, on European Commission, European Commission, December 11, 2019.

³ Frédéric Simon, The EU releases its Green Deal. Here are the key points, in Climate Home News, December 12, 2019.

⁴ Net-zero refers to the balance between the amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) that is produced and the amount that’s removed from the atmosphere. It can be achieved through a combination of emission reduction and emission removal.

Renovation Wave Strategy

Consistent with this aim, in **October 2020**, the Commission presented its Renovation Wave strategy¹ as part of the European Green Deal.

It contains a 2030 action plan to improve energy efficiency, boost the economy and deliver better living-standards for Europeans².

In more detail it sets specific goals with respect to 2015 levels, for the building sector to achieve the 55% target:

- decreasing greenhouse gas emissions by 60%;
- lowering final energy consumption by 14%;
- reducing energy consumption for heating and cooling by 18%.

The strategy to be adopted follows seven key principles:

1. energy efficiency;
2. affordability;

3. decarbonisation and integration of renewables;
4. life-cycle circularity;
5. health, safety, and environmental standards;
6. green and digital transition;
7. architectural quality.

It tackles the key barriers, at every point of the value chain, proposing a list of lead actions to enable the diffusion of deep renovations on a large scale.

Overall, the need is to at least double the annual energy renovation rate of all buildings resulting in around 35 million units renovated by 2030.

What emerges is that all supply chain must be properly considered, integrated and innovated to find a feasible retrofit model and strategy. Indeed, affordable renovations will help reducing energy bills and improving the health and wellbeing of vulnerable people, as later highlighted also in the Commission's recommendation on energy poverty, published in October 2023.

¹ European Commission COM(2020) 662 final, 2020a

² https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/renovation-wave_en, consulted on november 2024

1. The need for a new approach in renovation

The "Fit for 55" package of the European Union includes significant revisions of three key directives: the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED). These revisions are an integral part of the EU's efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030

compared to 1990 levels, with the goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Each directive aims to improve energy efficiency, promote the use of renewable energy, and reduce energy consumption, thus contributing to the transition towards a sustainable future.

How does it contribute to the goal of climate neutrality?

Buildings in the EU account for:

40% of final energy consumption

36% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions

Huge potential for cuts

Almost **75%** of existing buildings are inefficient in terms of energy and will require energy renovation on large scale

Less energy used
+ more green energy
= **fewer emissions**

EPBD

The **Energy Performance of Buildings Directive** (EPBD) was introduced in 2002 to improve energy performance in EU buildings. Revised in 2010 (Directive 2010/31/EU) and 2018 (Directive 2018/844/EU), it enhanced energy certification and promoted smart technologies and renewable energy. In 2021, the “Fit for 55” package proposed further revisions to accelerate renovations and reduce emissions. The latest revision, approved in May 2024, mandates zero-emission buildings by 2030.

The EPBD (2002/91/EC) is the first European legal act on energy policy in buildings, introduced in 2002.

It laid down the foundation for the setup of **minimum energy performance standards (MEPS)** in new buildings and in existing ones undergoing major renovation and having a useful floor area over 1000 m². Minimum energy performance standards are the first step to limit buildings consumptions, but they do not incentivise the pursuit of high energy efficiency. For this reason, 2002 EPBD introduced the concept of **Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)**, documents displaying the building’s energy performance through an energy class value or a continuous scale rating system.

The **2010 EPBD recast** brought in the concept of **Nearly Zero Energy Building (NZEB)** defined as “building of very high energy performance, where the nearly zero or very low amount of energy required should be covered to a very significant extent by

energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby” (art 9).

The EPBD was finally amended in **2018** to be in line with the 2030 climate goals¹. First, it established more effective Long-term Renovation Strategies (LTRS) at national level.

The most recent LTSRS starts from the NECPs 2030-roadmap to set up a long-term strategy supporting the building renovation towards a highly stock decarbonization by 2050.

In December 2021, another revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) has started, as part of the ‘Fit for 55’ package and as needed to deliver on the Renovation Wave (European Parliament, 2022). For the first time, it mentions the concept of “(staged) deep renovation”. A new definition of “zero-emission building” is also provided (Article 2).

Member States may choose buildings to target and measures to take, providing 55 % of the energy reduction is achieved by renovating the worst performing buildings. On minimum energy performance requirements, the law envisages that Member States renovate 16% of the worst performing non-residential buildings by 2030 and 26 % by 2033.

¹ Economidou et al., 2020

1. The need for a new approach in renovation

EED

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) was introduced in 2012 with the goal of improving energy efficiency in the European Union.

Launched as Directive 2012/27/EU, it aimed to achieve a 20% improvement in energy efficiency by 2020, setting measures to encourage the efficient use of energy across various sectors.

The revised **Energy Efficiency Directive (EU/2023/1791)** significantly raises the EU's ambition. It establishes **"energy efficiency first"** as a **fundamental principle of EU energy policy**, giving it legal standing for the first time.

In practical terms, this means that energy efficiency must be considered by EU countries in all relevant policy and major investment decisions taken in the energy and non-energy sectors.

The 2023 revision of the directive follows a proposal for a recast directive on energy efficiency put forward by the Commission in July 2021, as part of the EU Green Deal package.

The 2021 proposal was further enhanced as part of the REPowerEU plan, presented by the Commission in May 2022, aiming to decrease the EU's dependency on fossil fuel imports from Russia.

Full implementation of the Energy Efficiency Directive will be key for the EU to comply with the commitment of the Global Pledge to **double the global rate of energy efficiency improvements** from about 2% to over 4% by 2030.

The core of EED encompasses:

- the increase of EU energy efficiency target, by ensuring an additional 11.7% reduction in energy consumption by 2030, compared to the EU reference scenario 2020;

- the reduction of the total energy consumption of public bodies by 1.9% each year;

- the renovation of 3% of public buildings each year to NZEB or ZEB level.

The revised directive was published in the EU Official Journal and entered into force on 10 October 2023.

Roadmap energy efficiency directive (EED)

RED

The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) constitutes the legal framework for the development of clean energy in all sectors of the EU economy, with the objective of fostering cooperation between EU countries to achieve this goal.

The RED establishes a binding target of at least 42.5% of energy from renewable sources by 2030, with the aim of reaching 45%². This revision was deemed necessary to accelerate the EU's transition to clean energy, reduce greenhouse gas emissions and decrease dependence on fossil fuels, especially in light of the energy security concerns highlighted by the REPowerEU plan and the European Green Deal³.

The amending Directive EU/2023/2413 entered into force on 20 November 2023. A 18-month period has been designated for the transposition of the majority of the Directive's provisions into national law, with a more constrained deadline of July 2024 for certain provisions pertaining to the authorisation of renewable energy.

The legislative structure is intended to promote the development of clean energy across the EU economy. The transposition of the 11/2023 amendment to the RED into national law is also a requisite component of this process.

This transposition requires Member States to adopt specific measures to facilitate the authorisation and implementation of renewable energy projects, minimizing bureaucratic obstacles and accelerating approval times.

Additionally, the directive encourages cross-border cooperation among Member States, promoting

joint projects and the exchange of best practices. This collaborative approach is essential to achieving the EU's ambitious renewable energy targets and ensuring a fair and sustainable energy transition for all European citizens.

A more ambitious EU target for 2030

Old 2030 target at least
32% share

New 2030 target
42,5% share
+2,5% top-up

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/2413/oj/eng>

³ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en

1. The need for a new approach in renovation

New European Bauhaus

Beside the three main directives that set clear targets for national laws, the European Commission put in place also a broader initiative: the **New European Bauhaus (NEB)**.

It is a creative and interdisciplinary initiative that connects the European Green Deal to our daily lives and living spaces. It calls on all Europeans to imagine and build together a sustainable and inclusive future that is beautiful for our eyes, minds, and souls.

The New European Bauhaus was launched in 2021 to promote sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetically pleasing solutions to transform the built environment and living patterns, aligning with the ecological transition. The goal is to create livable spaces that respect the diversity of places, traditions, and cultures in Europe and beyond.

The initiative involves people at the grassroots level, focusing on neighborhoods and providing tools

and guidelines for tailored solutions to different communities. The NEB encourages the participation of citizens, experts, businesses, and institutions to imagine and build a sustainable and inclusive future that is **beautiful for the eyes, mind, and soul**.

Since 2021, the NEB has sparked a wave of creativity across the European Union, with projects aimed at improving the sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics of urban spaces. The European Commission has also presented investment guidelines to align projects with the NEB's transformative vision and has launched the NEB Academy to promote new skills and training in the sustainable construction sector.

Moreover, in 2024, the European Commission introduced the **NEB Investment Guidelines** to help investors align projects with the NEB's transformative vision. The Commission also launched the **NEB Academy**, an initiative to promote new skills and training in the sustainable construction sector. The second edition of the **New European Bauhaus Festival** took place in 2024, showcasing innovative projects and recognizing outstanding contributions.

https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/about-initiative_en

New European Bauhaus key-topics

- It is a **bridge** between the world of science and technology, art and culture.
- It is about **leveraging** our green and digital challenges to transform our lives for the better.
- It is an **invitation** to address complex societal problems together through co-creation.
- It facilitates and steer the transformation of our societies along three inseparable values:
 - **sustainability**, from climate goals to circularity, zero pollution, and biodiversity
 - **aesthetics**, quality of experience and style beyond functionality
 - **inclusion**, from valuing diversity to securing accessibility and affordability.

1.2 Current EU challenges

Introduction

Across the EU, there are **12 million non-residential buildings and 119 million residential buildings**, of which 42% are apartments, 34% detached dwellings, and 24% semi-detached dwellings, mostly located in urban centers (43%).

Around **48 million buildings**, representing 40%, **were built pre-1970**, before the widespread introduction of building codes and energy efficiency measures. It is also estimated that **35% of the whole stock has an EPC rating between D and G¹**, with around 30 million building units representing the 15% worst-performing ones across all Member States.

These data suggest that residential buildings still significantly contribute to the overall energy demand.

Indeed, they account for around **28%**, being as energy-demanding **as transport and more than industry (26%)²**. Housing is far from reaching 210 Mtoe, which corresponds to a 14% reduction in its final consumption, as stated in the Renovation Wave.

Efforts in energy efficiency and deep renovation are needed to achieve a decrease of 2% per year towards the 2030 objectives.

For the residential category, the above-mentioned 28% EU share, which corresponds to about 248 Mtoe of final energy consumed, employs several types of fuel for different household end-uses.

		Type of end-use					
		Space heating	Space cooling	Water heating	Cooking	Light and appliances	Other and uses
Fuel type	Energy use	62,80%	0,40%	15,10%	6,10%	14,50%	1%
Solid fossil fuels	2,8%	91,0%	0,0%	7,8%	1,1%	0,0%	0,0%
Derived heat	8,2%	77,0%	0,0%	2300,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
Oil and petroleum products	12,3%	78,2%	0,0%	14,6%	6,5%	0,0%	0,7%
Renewables and biofuels	20,3%	87,9%	0,0%	10,3%	1,2%	0,0%	0,7%
Electricity	24,7%	13,1%	1,5%	12,0%	12,5%	57,9%	3,0%
Natural gas	31,7%	74,6%	0,0%	19,3%	6,1%	0,0%	0,0%

1 Eurostat - Building Statistics

2 Eurostat - Energy Consumption

EU Commission, DG Energy, Unit A4

Overall, space heating is the end-use that requires the most energy (above 60%) and uses the highest share (around 75%) of natural gas, which is the most consumed non-renewable fuel.

This is why the **RED directive** set an ambitious **target of a 49% share of RES in the heating and cooling of buildings by 2030**. It is followed by both domestic hot water and lighting/appliances (15% each). On the contrary, space cooling doesn't reach 1% since it's needed only in a few countries located in the south of Europe.

The high share of renewables (20%), especially for heating systems, shows a positive trend towards 2030 objectives.

Indeed, in the EU, 39% of electricity generation comes from renewables and biofuels³.

Transposing the proportion to the residential sector, the renewable share would reasonably increase by 10% (being the 39% of 24.7%), to reach 30%.

It clearly emerges the need to drastically reduce the operational energy demand of the whole building sector by improving the performance of both the envelope and the technical systems, with particular attention to heating and cooling (due to the -18% target set by the Renovation Wave).

Indeed, to meet the Renovation Wave goal of decreasing greenhouse gas emissions by 60% with respect to 2015 levels, housing must reduce building-level releases by around 20 Mt CO₂ per year⁴.

This implies a yearly rate of 6.5%, which is possible only by combining energy efficiency measures and the implementation of renewable sources to cover the remaining needs.

³ European Commission - Renewable Energy Targets

⁴ European Commission - Renovation Wave

Social challenge

High energy consumption in buildings leads not only to unsustainable CO₂ emissions but also to unbearable energy bills, a phenomenon known as **energy poverty**. According to the European Energy Poverty Observatory (EPOV), energy poverty happens when energy bills form a significant portion of consumers' income, affecting their ability to cover other expenses. It can also occur when consumers are forced to reduce their energy consumption, impacting their physical and mental health.

A legislative definition was introduced for the first time in the 2021 EED recast proposal, defining energy poverty as a household's lack of access to essential energy services needed for a decent standard of living and health.

Energy poverty is a multi-dimensional issue caused by a combination of low income, high energy expenses, and poor energy efficiency in buildings. Various EU initiatives and laws address this issue within the framework of climate policies, such as the Renovation Wave, EED, EPBD, REpowerEU, and the Social Climate Fund, aiming to ensure a fair transition. Data collection and monitoring are essential to understand the full extent of the problem

and to implement effective policies. Given its complexity, energy poverty cannot be easily measured by a single indicator, necessitating the use of multiple parameters (high share of energy expenditure in income, low share of energy expenditure, inability to keep home adequately warm, and arrears on utility bills).

Eurostat data shows that in 2022, 9.3% of the EU population declared that they were not able to keep their home adequately warm. Compared with 2021, this share increased by 2.4 percentage points (pp).

The situation varied across the EU countries. The highest shares of people unable to keep their home adequately warm were registered.

Additionally, 6.5% of the EU population had arrears on their utility bills, indicating financial difficulties.

Such phenomenon got worst with the energy crisis, exacerbated by post-pandemic economic recovery and the war in Ukraine, which led to unprecedented levels of gas and electricity bills in 2022. Energy poverty affects health, well-being, social inclusion, and quality of life. Long-term strategies and structural measures are necessary to mitigate these effects and ensure a fair transition for all.

Inability to keep home adequately warm

Total

% of households

- ≥ 18.9 to 22.0
- ≥ 15.7 to 18.9
- ≥ 12.6 to 15.7
- ≥ 9.4 to 12.6
- ≥ 6.3 to 9.4
- ≥ 3.1 to 6.3
- ≥ 0.0 to 3.1

Economic challenge

In the construction sector, economic stagnation persists due to several factors: undercapitalization, horizontal and vertical fragmentation of the supply chain and low levels of profitability.

The sector is seeing declining labor market resilience and for three main reasons:

- 1. Aging of the workforce (soon more than 20% of the industry's workforce will be over 55 years old, while in 2030 the over-55 workforce will exceed 25%);**
- 2. Lack of skills and training;**
- 3. Low investment in innovation and digitalization.**

The construction sector's productivity is generally lower compared to other sectors in the European economy. In 2021, the apparent labor productivity in the building construction sector in the EU was €47,500 per person employed, lower than the average for the non-financial business economy of €60,200 per person employed¹. The labor productivity ratio adjusted for wages in the building construction sector was 138.0%, below the average for the non-financial business economy (154.4%) but above the average for the construction sector (119.9%). In 2022, productivity in the construction sector increased by 9.2%, surpassing the overall increase of 2.8%, with manufacturing productivity remaining relatively stable at 0.2%².

1 <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?oldid=327480>

2 https://www.euroconstruct.org/news/2023_06_it/

3 <https://fiec-statistical-report.eu/european-union>

4 <https://www.fiec.eu/library/publications/statistical-report>

5 <https://think.ing.com/articles/eu-construction-sector-faces-year-of-decline-but-green-shoots-appear/>

6 <https://fiec-statistical-report.eu>

7 https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/economic-forecast-and-surveys/economic-forecasts/autumn-2024-economic-forecast-gradual-rebound-adverse-environment_en

8 <https://www.property-forum.eu/news/europes-construction-sector-on-recovery-path-in-2025/19282>

As for the 19 countries analyzed by the institutes of the Euroconstruct network (Cresme for Italy), the forecast is that nonresidential construction will stagnate until 2024 and then resume growth³. Residential construction, on the other hand, will lose some of its market volume until 2024 and grow at a modest pace in the following years⁴. By 2025, housing construction is expected to fall to its lowest level since 2016⁵. Of the 19 countries under review, 17 are part of the Union. They are joined by Norway and Switzerland¹.

The reasons for this 'slowdown' are known:

- strong rise in interest rates and construction prices;
- persistently high inflation;
- loss of household purchasing power;
- weaker economic growth;
- tight government budgets;
- drop in real estate prices.

In addition, current real estate investment returns are hampering growth, as is the growing uncertainty in the commercial real estate sector⁶.

In 2023, non-residential construction in the EU grew by 1.5% but is expected to register very weak growth in 2024 (+0.3%)⁷. Residential construction is projected to decline by 5.7% in 2024, following a decline of 2.6% in 2023⁸. The construction sector in the EU is expected to contract by 2.3% in 2024. However, **some countries** like Greece and Lithuania **have shown significant growth in their construction sectors due to specific national recovery plans**.

1.3 Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) as a Solution

The environmental, social, and economic challenges described in the previous paragraphs point to the same conclusion: incremental renovation is insufficient. Europe's building stock requires a fundamentally different approach, one that is not merely faster or cheaper than the status quo, but capable of delivering scalable and replicable transformations.

The imperative for depth

Interventions on single building components — replacing a boiler, changing windows, adding roof insulation, or installing a photovoltaic system— deliver marginal improvements. They do not address the systemic energy inefficiency of the and they frequently lock in sub-optimal conditions for decades, foreclosing more ambitious upgrades later. Only deep renovation — properly defined in the next chapter — is capable of aligning existing buildings with EU climate neutrality targets.

Yet deep renovation, understood in the traditional sense, faces a fundamental paradox: its ambition is precisely what makes it difficult to be delivered at scale. Coordinating multiple trades, managing extended on-site durations, controlling quality across complex multi-system interventions, and financing large upfront investments have historically made deep renovation expensive, disruptive, slow and, consequently unsuited to the mass-market deployment.

The industrial response

Industrialized Deep Renovation resolves this paradox by applying the logic of industrial production to the renovation process. Rather than assembling building components one by one on an exposed construction site — subject to weather, coordination failures, skills gaps, and quality variability — IDR moves the production of key retrofit elements into controlled factory environments. The industrial logic also means that offsite approaches are inherently better suited to deep, multi-component interventions than to light retrofits. A façade panel integrating insulation, glazing, ventilation, energy generation, smart monitoring is only economically and technically justified when it replaces a significant share of the building's performance system in a single operation, addressing it holistically. This is why industrialization and deep renovation are strategies that are mutually reinforcing. The more ambitious the performance target, the greater the value of coordination, factory precision, and integrated system design.

Each additional component integrated into an off-site kit reduces the number of on-site trades, site visits, and coordination failures. It compresses the total intervention timeline. It reduces the disruption imposed on occupants. And it generates economies of scale both within a single project — because a higher proportion of value is generated in the factory — and across a pipeline of similar buildings, where standardized components can be produced in series at progressively lower unit costs.

A long-pursued ideal: from prefabrication to industrialization

Prefabrication has been an aspiration of the construction sector for well over a century, yet it has proven remarkably difficult to sustain. The Modern Movement of the early twentieth century was the first systematic attempt to apply industrial logic to building, drawing inspiration from the manufacturing revolution transforming other economic sectors. The urgency of the post-war housing emergency gave this ambition its greatest push: across Germany, France, the Netherlands, and much of Eastern Europe, large-scale prefabricated concrete load-bearing panels were deployed to rapidly house millions of people. The suburban housing estates built on this model still form a significant share of Europe's social housing stock today and, not coincidentally, represent some of the most energy-poor buildings now in need of deep renovation.

Indeed, its solutions were low-cost but architecturally rigid, offering little flexibility or aesthetic variety, and the systems never achieved the continuous improvement and adaptability that true industrialization requires. When the immediate hous-

ing emergency passed, the construction industry largely reverted to traditional in-situ methods.

The revival of prefabrication in the last two decades is qualitatively different from its predecessor, and this difference is what makes IDR more promising. Contemporary dry prefabricated systems — based on lightweight timber or metal frames, high-performance insulation layers, and integrated technical systems — bear little resemblance to the heavy concrete panels of the 1960s. More fundamentally, they are enabled by a technological infrastructure that did not exist before: digital design tools, numerically controlled manufacturing, BIM-based coordination, and mass customization platforms that allow industrially produced components to be precisely tailored to individual buildings without sacrificing the efficiency gains of factory production. Today, technology serves architecture and performance, rather than constraining them — a reversal of the relationship that is enabling the shift from prefabrication to industrialization. It is this digital precision that gives IDR its distinctive potential to deliver deep, high-quality, and replicable retrofits.

Renovation of Russoli social housing towers in Milan. Credits: Beatrice Arenella

2.

**What is
Industrialised
Deep
Renovation**

KEY TAKEAWAYS BOX

- Deep renovation, defined as achieving at least 75% reduction in primary energy consumption (below 60 kWh/m²/year), is the only renovation class aligned with EU climate neutrality targets, yet currently represents only 12% of the existing renovated stock.
- Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) combines the ambition of deep renovation with the efficiency of offsite manufacturing: components are produced in controlled factory environments and installed rapidly on site, dramatically reducing duration, disruption, and defects.
- IDR is a specialized subset of Modern Methods of Construction (MMC), a range of approaches which spans offsite, near site, and onsite pre-manufacturing, process improvements, and technology applications.
- BIM and DfMA are the two key enabling processes of IDR: BIM ensures digital coordination and efficient information exchange across the whole supply chain and full lifecycle, while DfMA ensures that components are designed from the outset to be manufactured efficiently offsite and assembled rapidly on site.
- IDR benefits operate at three levels: direct (shorter duration, higher quality, less disruption), indirect (lower lifecycle costs, higher asset value, better comfort), and systemic (economies of scale unlock further cost compression as renovation volumes grow).
- The main barriers to IDR adoption are high upfront costs, fragmented supply chains, limited trained workforce, complex regulatory frameworks, and insufficient financial models for long-term performance guarantees.

A comparison between different types of renovation

KPI	Traditional light Renovation	Deep Renovation	Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR)
Definition	Single or partial element upgrades using conventional on-site construction methods, without a whole-building performance target, typically driven by obsolescence.	Coordinated, multi-element intervention targeting significant reduction in primary energy consumption, typically delivered through traditional on-site methods.	Whole-building, deep performance upgrade delivered through offsite-manufactured, integrated components having the efficiency and scalability of industrial production
Scope of intervention	Single element (e.g., windows or roof insulation only)	Multiple elements, coordinated but not integrated	Whole-building, integrated (envelope, systems and renewables)
On-site installation speed	Weeks to months, depending on the type of intervention	More than a year	Days to weeks (e.g., façade in 8–15 days)
Disruption to occupants	Depending on the type of intervention	High due to multiple works to be done onsite and inside the building	Low to minimal (often inhabited throughout, most of works from the outside)
Design process	Sequential, low upfront investment	Coordinated, moderate upfront effort	Front-loaded, highly coordinated (BIM/DfMA-driven)
Quality control	Variable, site-dependent	Moderate and limited to single components	High: factory-controlled, tested before installation
Performance guarantee	Standard according to the intervention	Usually, 5 to 10 years against major damages	Often contractual (20–30 years via EPC/EPC+)
Upfront capital requirement	Moderate	High	High but manageable via EPC+/PPP financial models
Asset value impact	Minor	Positive due to energy class improvements	Strongly positive also due to high-quality of installed elements
Energy performance improvement	20–40% reduction	≥75% reduction at design stage	≥75% reduction, verified and often guaranteed
Primary energy consumption post-renovation	>100 kWh/m ² /year	<60 kWh/m ² /year	<60 kWh/m ² /year, often approaching net-zero
Maintenance costs (30-year horizon)	High and unpredictable	Reduced thanks to installation of new systems	Significantly reduced thanks to durable components (up to 25% lower)
Scalability / replicability	Medium, given the simplicity of single-element interventions	Low: each project bespoke and building-specific	High: standardized solutions for similar buildings enabling economies of scale

2.1 Definition of IDR

The meaning of deep

As emerged from the European Renovation Wave strategy and legislation, deep renovation is a policy goal of the EU and its Member States. Currently, the renovation rate for deep interventions is only around 0.2%,¹ while the annual weighted renovation rate (including light, medium, and deep ones) reaches 1.0%.² So far, only about 12% of the residential building stock has been renovated to meet the targets³. To achieve climate neutrality by 2050, the renovation rate should increase to 3%, with deep retrofits accounting for 70% of the total⁴.

The **Global Buildings Performance Network (GBPN)** followed a tiered research approach to clarify and harmonize the concept of deep renovation (GBPN, 2013). According to the results of the GBPN process, the following conclusions have been drawn:

- Targets for deep renovation should be set in both relative and absolute terms. However, they require further specifications on the building type, the energy class, and the location. Indeed, relative targets depend on the initial building's condition and age, while the absolute ones should vary according to the climate zone.
- CO₂ emissions reduction targets can be omitted even if they're the final objective since they are strictly linked to the decrease in the energy consumed by the building stock.

- Primary and final energy targets should be specified to encourage savings in both energy generation and building operations. Priority is given to a clear primary savings goal because it's directly linked to the total emissions.
- In the European Union, the most widely accepted and validated definition of deep renovation sets energy reductions at 75% or more compared to the status of the existing building before the retrofit⁵. Primary energy consumption after renovation should be less than 60 kWh/m²/year⁶.

“Deep renovation” means a renovation in line with the energy efficiency first principle and efforts to reduce whole life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions generated during the renovation⁷.

This approach focuses on essential building elements such as wall insulation, roof insulation, low floor insulation, replacement of external joinery, ventilation and heating systems, and treatment of thermal bridges to ensure the necessary comfort of the occupants in both summer and winter.

1 https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/renovation-wave_en

2 https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/content/bpie_renovation_wave_analysis_052021_final.pdf

3 <https://www.iea.org/policies/12766-european-commissions-renovation-wave-strategy>

4 https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/eu_renovation_wave_strategy_0.pdf

5 <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/40299428-f65d-11eb-9037-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

6 https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC122347/epbd_report_12.07-rev-27-07-2.pdf

7 Art.2 of the recast EPBD (European Parliament, 2023a); https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en

What is Deep Renovation?

Deep Renovation is an integrated renovation approach that captures the full energy potential of improvement works on existing buildings and leads to very high energy performance.

Moderate Renovation

Involving typically more than three improvements to existing buildings which result in energy reductions of 30% to 60%.

Deep Renovation

Enabled through high-grade improvements that can result in energy savings ranging between 60% to 90% and costing on average between 140 €/m² and 330 €/m² respectively.

VS

Outcomes of Deep Renovation?

Heightened energy performance, ensured consistency retrofits, and fully integrated implementation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 892071

In the draft of the recast EPBD (European Parliament, 2023a), wanted by the 2021 Fit for 55 package, deep renovation is introduced, for the first time, among the directive's definitions, in Article 2⁷.

It is a renovation resulting in a reduction of at least 60%⁷ in primary energy demand for worst-performing buildings for which it is technically and economically not feasible to achieve a zero-emission building standard, and which transforms a building or building unit:

- before 1 January 2027, into a nearly zero-energy building;
- from 1 January 2027, into a zero-emission building.

A good alternative to the deep **retrofit made** all at once is to face it **step by step, the so called "Staged**

renovation". This means that the interventions are carried out at different moments and therefore the costs incurred are spread over time.

An important point to keep in mind when using this approach is to plan each intervention in advance, in order to keep the holistic overview of the deep retrofit and orient each intervention to the final goal.

To do this, several tools can be used to facilitate the process. For example, a good way to approach step by step retrofit is to use the **kits** developed by INFINITE project (see the introductory chapter "About the project").

The meaning of industrialized

Moving from the performances and savings to be achieved within each deep retrofit to the way it should be carried out, industrialized renovation acquires significant relevance.

It refers to a new approach based on offsite construction methods: the production of retrofit solutions and components is moved away from the job site to a controlled factory environment, at an industrial scale ⁸.

Industrialized renovation is a specific application within the wider family of Modern Methods of Construction (MMC) — a term that originated in the United Kingdom and has since gained broader European currency ⁹. The need to increase prefabrication in the housing sector was discussed, drawing on experiences from the manufacturing industry, to identify how to improve efficiency, reduce waste, and make the sector more responsive to changing

needs.

MMC is defined as “a range of approaches which span offsite, near site, and onsite pre-manufacturing, process improvements, and technology applications.”

It is therefore a broad umbrella encompassing 7 main categories that potentially improve construction productivity, ranging from fully volumetric three-dimensional modules to incremental process efficiency at construction sites. **Industrialized renovation**, which focuses primarily on the prefabrication of building envelope components and integrated building systems - including photovoltaic, windows and/or other technical ducks or equipment - corresponds above all to the **non-structural sub-assembly category** (number 5 in the picture), meaning 2D elements installed on an existing structural shell. Where buildings have specific technical constraints or surface irregularities, site-based processes (categories 6 and 7 in the picture) are used to optimize the work.

⁸ European Commission: https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/content/industrial_prefabrication_solutions_for_building_renovation_final-version.pdf

⁹ Uk Government: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/modern-methods-of-construction-workinggroup-developing-a-definition-framework>

2. What is Industrialised Deep Renovation

Within common professional usage, however, several terms are employed that describe related but technically distinct realities. While they are often used interchangeably in everyday language, understanding their nuances helps clarify the nature of the solutions being proposed:

- **Industrialized** refers to a production approach that applies industrial principles — systematic process organization, division of labor, quality control, standardization, automation, and economies of scale — to the manufacturing of construction components. The emphasis is on factory methods, numerical control machinery, and repeatable processes that reduce variability and cost per unit as volumes grow.
- **Offsite** describes the physical location of production. Components are manufactured away from the construction site, in a factory or workshop. Offsite construction may or may not be highly industrialized in the strict sense — a small workshop producing bespoke timber elements is offsite but not necessarily industrial-scale. The term draws attention to the separation between production and installation environments, including the logistical challenge of transporting and assembling components on site.
- **Prefabricated** refers to components that are assembled or finished prior to installation, as opposed to being built in place element by element. Prefabrication can occur offsite (in a factory) or near-site (in a temporary assembly area adjacent to the building). It implies a degree of pre-completion — windows glazed, insulation fitted, services integrated — that reduces on-site labour and time. Prefabrication reminds of an approach already widely experimented from the 1960s onwards, primarily through heavy pre-cast concrete elements offering limited architectural flexibility and no meaningful customization. Contemporary prefab renovation goes significantly further, combining factory precision with digital design to deliver components that are both highly performant and architecturally responsive.

- **Modular** describes a design logic based on standardized, interchangeable units, - called modules - that can be combined in different configurations to address varying building geometries and performance requirements. Modularity enables flexibility within a standardized system: the same module type can be adapted, stacked, or combined differently across different buildings, supporting both mass customization and economies of scale. Modular renovation solutions are typically prefabricated and often produced offsite, but the defining feature is the system logic of interchangeable units rather than the production logic per se.

DfMA and BIM as key enabling processes

Two cross-cutting processes are essential to making IDR work in practice, regardless of which specific technical solution is adopted.

Design for Manufacture and Assembly (DfMA) is a design methodology that integrates manufacturing and assembly considerations from the very earliest stages of a project³. Rather than designing a building component for optimal performance in isolation and then figuring out how to build it, DfMA requires designers, engineers, and manufacturers to work together from the outset — asking, for every design choice, whether the resulting component can be efficiently produced in a factory, transported to site, and installed rapidly and safely. In renovation, this means that façade panels are designed also for ease the manufacturing process (minimizing custom cuts, optimizing material use), compatibility with the existing building structure (standard connection details, minimal on-site adjustment), and speed of assembly (crane-ready formats, pre-integrated systems). DfMA disciplines the entire design process toward industrializability and it has many advantages¹⁰:

¹⁰ Design for Manufacturing and Assembly (DfMA) in Construction: A Holistic Review of Current Trends and Future Directions

- Most of the work is carried out in the factory, under safer conditions and with better quality control;
- The few remaining on-site operations are faster, cleaner, and require less labour;
- There is less waste, given the high level of precision in the production of the prefabricated product and the performance is higher as it does not depend on manual work on site;
- DfMA components can be more easily dismantled at the end of their useful life and destined for reuse or recycling.;

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a digital process in which a coordinated, data-rich three-dimensional model of the building serves as the shared reference platform for all project stakeholders (architects, structural engineers, energy modelers, manufacturers, installers, and facility managers). In the context of IDR, BIM is not merely a visualization tool: it is the digital backbone that makes the industrialized process possible. It enables the precise geometric survey of the existing building — critical for fitting prefabricated panels to irregular or aged surfaces — and integrates architectural, structural, energy, and production engineering variables into a single model. BIM is then used to generate shop drawings for factory production, optimize logistics and installation sequences, and run energy and comfort simulations before a single component is manufactured. After completion, the BIM model becomes the basis for the building’s operational management and preventive maintenance, enabling the performance guarantees that are a defining feature of IDR contracts. Without BIM-enabled coordination, the precision required for large-scale, multifunctional offsite renovation would be unattainable.

Together, DfMA and BIM form the digital and methodological infrastructure on which Industrialized Deep Renovation depends, enabling speed, quality, cost-efficiency, and performance certainty at scale.

Approches that enable industrialised renovation

2.2 Benefits and challenges

Benefits

So far, the potential benefits (such as time, safety, cost, quality, etc.) of innovative practices have been investigated and quantified primarily for new offsite construction, even if also industrialized renovation has a broad range of advantages with respect to traditional methods. In the list below, and in the following picture are reported all the IDR benefits grouped in three categories:

1. **Direct advantages** which are strictly related to a deep industrialized retrofit and differentiate it from a light and traditional intervention. The time frame considered is just the short term, from the design stage till onsite renovation works.
2. **Indirect benefits** that are related to broader project impacts, linked to direct advantages, and leading to parameters that can be economically quantified and valorised. They take into account the whole building lifecycle and different stakeholders' categories (owner, tenants, workers, society).
3. **Economies of scale** which come into play when more than one project is involved, as long as a pipeline of similar and clustered buildings renovations is planned. These advantages can be split among solution providers, general contractors and stock owners or developers.

1. Direct benefits

Design

- **High project performance:** optimized energy efficiency, seismic safety, and better air quality is ensured through innovative solutions;
- **Up-front planning:** comprehensive early-stage coordination implies precise implementation and enhanced process efficiency.

Manufacturing

- **Controlled environment:** producing components in factories guarantees higher product quality and precision;
- **Improved durability:** prefabrication results in more robust and reliable components, extending their operational lifespan;
- **Better quality:** factory-tested materials ensure fewer defects and closer adherence to specifications.

Transport

- **Logistic optimization:** centralized production enables to better plan and organize the transportation of components, lowering the number of trips to site.

Construction

- **Shorter retrofit duration:** simultaneous offsite manufacturing and onsite preparation gives greater certainty in construction program and reduced risk of delays.

2. Indirect benefits

- **Long-term performance guarantee:** quality-controlled manufacturing ensures that design performances are met in the long-term;
- **Lower energy consumption:** high-efficiency components reduce operational energy needs;
- **Lower utility bills:** decreased energy usage translates directly into cost savings for residents;
- **Better insurance conditions:** reduced risks associated with standardized construction methods enhance insurance terms;
- **Reduced depreciation risk:** high-quality materials and durability minimize property value depreciation;
- **Increased property value:** energy and performance upgrades enhance long-term asset market value according to its location;
- **Better indoor comfort:** improved insulation, air quality, and temperature control increase occupant satisfaction;
- **Reduced maintenance costs:** standardized, durable components reduce the frequency and cost of repairs;
- **Lower healthcare costs:** better indoor conditions improve tenants' health and reduce associated costs;
- **Safer working conditions:** factory settings minimize onsite hazards, improving worker safety;
- **Less waste:** controlled production processes reduce material waste and optimize scraps reuse;
- **Lower traffic:** fewer transport trips to sites decrease congestion and emissions;
- **Reduced emissions:** optimized logistics and energy-efficient guaranteed products lower environmental impacts;
- **Reduced carbon tax:** certifiable efficient energy use and lower emissions lead to tax benefits;
- **Better financial conditions:** guaranteed process and solutions improve access to green financing options;
- **Minimal disruptions:** reduced onsite activity leads to less noise and inconvenience for residents;
- **Lower reallocation costs:** limited construction time allows tenants to avoid relocation;
- **Reduced temporary works:** prefabrication minimizes the need for scaffolding and onsite facilities;
- **Lower site costs:** prefabrication reduces onsite time, labor and associated overhead.

3. Economies of scale

- **Process standardization:** prefabrication fosters repeatability and efficient resource use across projects
- **Faster retrofits:** modular and offsite techniques accelerate the renovation process and rate.
- **Lower costs:** industrialized production reduces individual project design and manufacturing expenses
- **Higher productivity:** centralized and efficient operations lead to better overall profitability

Challenges

Besides the wide range of advantages given by off-site techniques, industrialized deep renovation still faces several key challenges that hinder its widespread adoption. Such barriers can be summarized as follow:

- From a FINANCIAL point of view, IDR implies **high upfront costs**. Initial investment for prefabricated materials and advanced processes is a significant deterrent for both private and public customers. There is, then, a strong need for **new financial models** that enable the real implementation of better financial conditions, like green loans or pay-for-performance models. In this regard, assessing the long-term performance of innovative renovations can be complex and challenging since it requires monitoring multiple parameters for which it can be difficult to establish universal thresholds due to the variability of building typologies, climates and users' behaviors. Finally, being a quite new practice, offsite renovation is linked to **uncertainty in return on investment**, which can deter investors and building owners.
 - From a TECHNICAL AND OPERATIONAL perspective, industrialized approaches imply structural changes in the workflow, starting from a **higher effort in upfront planning** and design with lower design flexibility throughout the renovation phase. In addition, the **digitalization of the processes** is also essential but tools like BIM (Building Information Modeling) and digital twin technologies demand significant investment and expertise. Nowadays, **supply chains are too fragmented**. The lack of standardized processes and coordination among stakeholders slows down the scalability of industrialized renovations and constructions. **A shortage of trained installers and skilled workforce also** prevent the kick in on innovative approaches. Indeed, advanced renovation techniques require training in digital tools, sustainable materials, and efficient project and production management, which may not yet be widespread.
 - Moving to the DEMAND AND BEHAVIORAL side, there is a **diffused skepticism**. Building owners, tenants, and contractors hesitate to adopt new technologies or methods due to perceived risks and resistance to modular and prefabricated solutions due to perceptions of poor quality or lack of adaptability. **Engaging tenants** (before, during and after the renovation) addressing their concerns about disruptions, cost-sharing, energy savings and rent changes is also a crucial but complex process. Actually, the actions of the inhabitants have a major impact on the performance of the building during the use phase, and they can help to make the most out of the proposed innovations if they are properly trained in the correct management of the house.
 - Considering REGULATORY barriers, there is a **lack of policy support**. Insufficient incentives, subsidies, or supportive legislation hinder the adoption of innovative retrofit practices. **Inadequate building codes** may not align with deep and offsite renovation goals, creating barriers to compliance. Finally, **current procurement procedures** often favor traditional methods, making it difficult for industrialized approaches to compete due to their different cost structures and implementation requirements.
- Overall, overcoming these barriers will require coordinated efforts, including financial innovation, workforce development, digital upskilling, tenant engagement strategies, and strong policy frameworks to enable industrialized deep renovation to scale effectively leading to cost reductions through wide market spread.

3.

IDR Best practices

KEY TAKEAWAYS BOX

- Energiesprong is the most successful and widely replicated IDR model in Europe, now active in the Netherlands, France, Germany, the UK, and Italy, with over 20.000 interventions delivering consistent results: >50% energy savings, >75% carbon reduction, and lower disruption for inhabitants, versus traditional approaches.
- Each national Energiesprong program has adapted the approach to its local building stock, regulatory environment, and market maturity, creating insightful business, financial, procurement and technical models.
- The EPC+ contractual model — where an ESCo funds the retrofit upfront and recoups investment through guaranteed energy savings — is the most financially innovative and socially inclusive model tested, eliminating upfront capital barriers for building owners while ensuring long-term performance.
- Total Cost of Ownership analysis over 30 years consistently confirms that industrialized solutions become economically superior to traditional renovation approaches in the medium term, with a 10–20% advantage in the advanced scenario incorporating economies of scale.
- Besides Energiesprong or other Country-specific initiatives, European funded projects, including H2020 INFINITE, enable the financing of integrated technical and economic innovation, that can be applied to pilot projects to close the gap between research and market, before being replicated.

3.1 The EU IDR stakeholder map

The application of industrialized deep renovation has been largely investigated in the **literature**, even if offsite new construction is still much more known and examined.

Beside the ongoing academic investigations, current practice tends to deal with minor and single interventions (e.g., wall or roof insulation, window replacement, installation of new boilers or heat pumps, integration of a photovoltaic system, etc.) that are implemented without an overall coordination and organic vision of the whole building performance. The reason is linked to several barriers that involve technical, financial, and social aspects of IDR, as explained in the previous paragraph. In recent years, such obstacles have been mainly addressed by various **research projects financed by the European Union**. Indeed, they do not only focus on the development of prefabricated technology sets, but they also tackle viable financial, business and operational models.

Furthermore, throughout Europe, private initiatives of **pioneering companies developing prototyped industrialized solutions** for new buildings and deep retrofits are on the rise.

As a result, the R&D departments of different companies (manufacturers of façade panels, windows, ventilation equipment, photovoltaics, etc.) collaborate and launch new integrated elements on the market, testing them on private and small-to-medium-sized buildings.

Even if, most of the currently developed offsite manufacturing uses relatively traditional production lines, there is growing investment in automated plants from the leading players ¹¹.

This bottom-up trend shows a growing interest in the industrialization of the building process on the part of the supply side but does not provide the sector with a strategic scaling-up of interventions towards a common, widespread approach.

Taking into account the intrinsic limitations of scattered market initiatives or single pilot projects, Energiesprong is the most successful and diffused industrial prefabrication movement for deep renovation to date.

This retrofit model, born in the Netherlands, has several applications worldwide as a technically and economically sustainable model that can be replicated on a large scale ¹². It quickly spread to France, Germany, the UK, and even Italy, and has been awarded several prizes: in 2018, it received the Global Green Building Entrepreneurship Award; in 2019, it was recognized as European Energy Innovation of the Year; and most recently, in 2024, it won the World Habitat Award ¹³.

To summarize, the map on the right allows to highlight both the Countries having already developed an active IDR market (Energiesprong in dark green) and the Countries having applied IDR technologies on pilot projects (thanks to Horizon funds, light blue). The latter are still quite relevant because they are the upcoming “candidates” to scale up IDR in Europe.

¹¹ <https://www.unido.org/news/unidos-regional-launch-industrial-development-report-2024-eastern-europe>

¹² https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/unido-publications/2023-11/IDR24-OVERVIEW_1.pdf

¹³ <https://Energiesprong.org/why-the-end-is-just-the-beginning-when-retrofitting-homes/>

- Countries implementing Energiesprong market initiative
- Countries having tested a IDR technology Horizon pilot projects

3.2 The Energiesprong movement

Energiesprong is a **deep industrialized renovation program** that uses a comprehensive supply chain approach to enable the achievement of net-zero energy and attractive retrofits by implementing offsite technologies such as prefabricated facades with windows and ventilation system integrations, insulated rooftops with solar thermal and photovoltaic panels and smart heating and cooling installations.

The refurbishment comes with rapid onsite installation and a long-year warranty on building performances. Retrofitting according to the Energiesprong model means turning a high energy house into a house that is able to generate its own energy for heating, hot water and household appliances, and to provide a higher level of indoor comfort.

The experience of the first **20.000 interventions** across Europe has shown that it is possible to reduce energy consumption by more than 50%, lower costs by 30% and decrease the carbon footprint of the building by more than 75% compared to the baseline. These results are more significant than any other retrofit approach currently used in Europe.

The Energiesprong workflow starts from the analysis of the building until the end of its useful life. The digitalization of the process allows significant optimization of time and human resources with consequent compressions in costs expected overall costs in proportion to renovated volumes. As shown in the picture, After the **analysis** phase of the building to be retrofitted, a digital twin model is created, and the **DESIGN** phase can start. **Bim** is used to integrate architectural, structural and production engineering variables, as well as to carry out the necessary energy and anti-seismic simulations. The digital project is then transformed into shop drawings for the factory **production** of the offsite elements, the **logistics** optimization and the management of the onsite **WORKS**, assemblies and installations. The twin model, suitably revised once the tests are completed, becomes the basis for the **use and preventive maintenance** phase of the renovated building. The management of this and the **end-of-life** phases are facilitated by offsite and controlled production of the components which leads to high guaranteed performances levels with an expected increase in the residual value of the building.

Overall Energiesprong renovation is:

DECARBONIZED

since it's a deep intervention in line with the European 2030 and 2050 targets.

SAFE

because it aims to ensure improved energy and seismic performance, as well as greater safety on construction sites.

SCALABLE

because it aims to reduce costs and execution times by industrialising processes and guaranteeing optimal performance in the long term.

DESIDERABLE

because it reduces the time spent on site and eliminates the need for scaffolding. It also ensures improved indoor comfort and quality finishes.

Industrialized deep renovation outlook

Cost/benefit comparison of the Energiesprong and light and deep retrofit with a traditional approach.

From an economic perspective, in the Energiesprong model, the renovation is financed by future savings in energy costs, which are added to those of the planned maintenance over the guaranteed period of around 30 years without net additional investment expenditure to tenants, as shown in the bar chart.

This new business model is based on the concept of **Total Cost of Ownership** which makes it possible to overcome the logic of minimum initial capital expenditure and aims to evaluate the investment with a **Life Cycle Cost approach**. In this regard, the extra costs resulting from industrialized and high-quality products are offset by the economic advantages generated by the unique benefits of Energiesprong (listed in the previous chapter).

On the one hand, by replicating the interventions on a largescale, it will be possible to reduce the costs of the prefabricated elements, in proportion to the quantities produced, thanks to industrial optimizations.

On the other hand, for a correct analysis, it is necessary to consider the value generated by the monetization of the different benefits, for the different actors involved in the different phases of the renovation process.

Beside the general economic model, each Country developed the Energiesprong movement according to the availability of national funds, peculiarities of the building stock, local opportunities and strategic priorities. In the next pages, an overview of modalities and achievements in the Netherlands, France, United Kingdom, Germany and Italy is presented.

The Netherlands

Implementation date	2010-2016 2017-on going
Market development team	Platform 31, non profit network of organization Stroomversnellingn non profit association
Funding structure	50 million (government 2010-2016) 6 billion (WAW Social Bank loan) 3.6 million shared (transition Zero, H2020 2016-2019) 11.6 million shared (Must-be0, Interreg, 2019-2020)
Achieved results	5700 retrofitted houses

According to the overview made by the European Construction Sector Observatory (European Commission, 2017), Energiesprong was commissioned by the Dutch Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations through € 50 million government funding¹ (distributed from 2010 till 2016) to meet the objectives of the Innovation Agenda for the Built Environment, a compilation of innovative policies focused on construction and energy transition. Energiesprong’s first goal was to create the conditions for affordable net-zero energy retrofits to take hold in the mass market by 2020. It targeted to deliver solutions to 2.500 new buildings, making them energy-neutral, and 2.500 renovated ones, allowing them to reach from 45% to 80% energy savings.

The first retrofits were piloted on terraced houses, and they **achieved**:

- 150 kwh/m2 (**70% of total reduction in energy consumption**) from 20.000 kWh to 6.000 kWh;
- **1/3 savings** generated by the energy produced **on-site** and **2/3 savings** coming **from energy efficiency measures**;
- a cost of 130.000 € per unit.

By the end of 2013, thanks to economy of scale, 3D technologies and prefabricated materials, the

cost per terraced house lowered to about 65.000 €, getting closer to the 40.000 € target. Overall, the accomplished energy savings have been:

- 45% in 800 existing houses
- 60% in 160 existing houses
- 80% in 258 existing houses

In 2013, Energiesprong also brokered the **“Stroomversnelling”** (rapids) **deal between six housing associations, four construction companies and other supporting organizations to retrofit to Net Zero Energy (NZE) 111.000 social housing dwellings (11.000 confirmed agreements with the prospect of a further 100.000)** divided into: terraced houses; four-story buildings and multi-apartments blocks, according to the scale up strategy shown in the figure below in the previous page. The three categories have a growing degree of complexity given by the rising number of floors which increase the height of the retrofit interventions and decreases the roof surface available per dwelling for the installation of renewable energy sources to supply enough electricity for heating, hot water and appliances. Therefore, while terraced houses renovation have potentially reached the mass market, the innovation of technical solutions should be mature enough to be tested on the first prototypes for multi-apartments blocks. Stroomversnelling required an investment of € 6 billion, funded by the WSW Social Bank through a 40-year government-backed loan to the involved housing associations.

In 2014, while the market development team grew from 3 to 45 people, the number of housing associations part of the deal increased from 6 to 27, resulting in 200 pilot retrofits delivered.

In 2015, together with the roll-out of 2000 more renovation interventions, Stroomversnelling evolved into a **standing market initiative** becoming a network of more than 65 members among contractors, component suppliers, housing providers, local governments, financiers, energy system managers and other parties with the aim of increasing the

¹ European Commission (2017) European Construction Sector Observatory - Policy fact sheet - Netherlands - Energiesprong (Energy Leap) - Thematic Objectives 1 & 3.

pace of growth of NZE retrofits. In the meanwhile, other Countries joined the Energiesprong movement, establishing their own market development teams while the Netherlands expanded the NZE retrofit approach to commercial offices, schools, and care homes.

Dutch government funding ended in 2016 but additional economic support to the whole Energiesprong network has been obtained through three EU research projects for a total of € 20,6 million among 5 Countries (€3,6 M for H2020 Transition Zero between NL, FR, UK; €5,4 M for Interreg North-West Europe E=0 between NL, FR, UK, LU; €11,6 M for Interreg North-West Europe MustBe0 between NL, FR, UK, DE).

Besides the EU subsidy programs, Stroomversneling is funded by all its members (institutions, housing associations, solution providers) and by the European Climate Foundation, a philanthropic fundraising initiative to foster the development of a net-zero emissions society. To date **at least 5.700 houses have been retrofitted but many more have not been traced.**

In addition, being the most advanced Energiesprong country **it has already monitored several houses** on execution, delivery and usage. In particular, the monitoring of 46 homes in Heerhugowaard and 18 in Tilburg, shows that on average the actual energy performances match the design specifications, meaning that the guarantees are respected². Space heating usage solar production have been a little more than expected. In some cases, among early projects there has been insufficient air tightness due to some problems with the panels' installation and also bad quality products of one specific company. Such issues are inevitable in the first interventions, but monitoring is crucial to quickly address the problem and improved the upcoming design. It was also helpful to spot too high consumptions among occupants who were consequently educated to avoid higher energy bills. In addition, several aspects of tenant satisfaction were measured: they were generally satisfied with the retrofit result but less happy about the overall process. These first monitored projects explicated the need to incorporate occupants wish in the intervention, clearly communicate with them and properly manage their expectations.

2 Energiesprong, 2019

France

Implementation date	2016-on going
Market development team	Greenflex, sustainability consultancy company
Funding structure	3.6 million shared (transition Zero, H2020 2016-2019) 5.4 million shared (E=0, Interreg, 2016-2019) 11.6million shared (Mustbe0, Interreg, 2019-2022) ADEME, the French Environment and Energy Efficiency Agency Caisse des Dépôts
Achieved results	4200 retrofitted houses

In March 2016, Energiesprong was launched in France, together with the beginning of Transition Zero and E=0 projects which have, among others, the objective to **create early markets for net zero energy refurbishments using frontrunner social housing organizations** in France and United Kingdom. The market development team is hosted by GreenFlex, a sustainability consultancy company specialised in helping organisations to accelerate their social and environmental transition. GreenFlex has set up a market development team of 7 people to adapt and implement the Energiesprong approach with local stakeholders¹. The first two project renovated, funded by E=0 project, are 10 houses in Hem (housing provider: Vilogia, general contractor: Rabot Dutilleul Construction, intervention: from class F to class A spending € 1.200.000) and 12 units in Longueau (housing provider: ICF Habitat, general contractor: Bouygues, intervention: from class F to class A spending € 1.500.000)². These first demonstrators have inspired others, within the MustBeZero project and beyond: 64 stakeholders, among which 14 housing associations, have signed a charter engaging them to contribute to the Energiesprong dynamics in France. Financing has been obtained also from ADEME (The French Environment and Energy Efficiency Agency) and Caisse

des Dépôts, which plays a major role in financing social housing, energy transition and smart city developments.

Of particular importance is the renovation of 988 apartments, spread over 9 buildings of 11 storeys each, commissioned by Est Métropole Habitat near Lyon in 2020. The panels on the east façade were installed by crane in just 8 days without the need for scaffolding, demonstrating the feasibility of industrialised interventions on multi-storey residential buildings³.

Beside scattered project, the recently born MASH (Mutualisation d’Achat au Service de l’Habitat) initiative represents the first purchasing centre for industrialized and guaranteed zero-energy renovations and it was driven by the Social Union for Housing in Pays de la Loire. It promotes the pooling of purchases and the coordination of actors, thank to which social landlords can carry out large-scale renovations and achieve ambitious objectives in terms of energy efficiency. For the first time, 14 social landlords have come together within a central purchasing body to launch a group order for Energiesprong renovations addressing approximately 2000 homes. The dwellings have been divided into 5 lots of a few hundred units each.

The renovation works took place in a staggered and progressive manner, allowing all companies, whether small or large, to participate to these first aggregated call for tenders⁴.

To conclude, Energiesprong France has put a lot of effort in **monitoring and analysing the market development** to redact the first Observatory of Costs, Quality and Impact of Energiesprong renovations aimed at establishing trajectories based on project data⁵. Six major housing types have been identified

1 Energiesprong FR, 2023a

2 EU Interreg NWE project E=0, 2020

3 Energiesprong FR, 2023c

4 Energiesprong FR, 2023b

5 Energiesprong FR, 2021

for mass industrialized renovation, starting from 22 typologies characterized by different construction periods and different geographical locations. There are 3 categories of detached houses and 3 of multi-family buildings, for a total of 14 million units suitable for interventions. In addition, for each of the dimension analysed has compared Energiesprong renovation with 3 other scenarios: minimum maintenance, traditional renovation,

and demolition/new construction. The main fundings are summarized below in the pictures “COST”, “QUALITY” and “IMPACT”.

Considering an average social housing stock, the advantages of Energiesprong renovations in terms of overall cost and carbon impact over 30 years, with respect to the other scenarios are aggregated in the graph.

Cost

- Prices are already falling, with a -20% reduction for current projects compared to the first projects;
- Observatory data can be used to drift thr price trajectory and asses likely prices for mass markets. Single family housing retrofits will cost around €900 / m²VAT excluded (-40% compared with initialprojects), while multi family housing willbe about €700 / m²VAT excluded (-55% compared with initialprojects);
- In terms of overall cost over 30 years, Energiesprong offers the best performance/cost ratio compared with the other scenarios.

Quality

- The solutions implemented on the pilot projects enabled to achive and even surpass the goal of zero energy for uses
- (production > consumption);
- Heating requirements are reduced by 75% compared with the existing system;
- Numerous high-performance solutions are emerging. They present commonfeatures such as the use of integrated and prefabricated solutions and a growingshare of bio-sourced materials.

Impact

- Compared with the other scenarios the carbon impact of an Energiesprong renovation is the lowest, inboth multi-family and single-family housing;
- An Energiesprong intervention reduces the total carbon inimpact of an home over 30 years by 35% (considering all greenhouse emissions and not just those associated with energy consumption), compared with a minimum maintenance scenario;
- This reduction can reach 50% when the most carbon free constructive solutions are implemented (such as bio-sourced prefabricated facade and roofs);
- For E, F and G homes, decrease in carbon impact can get to75%, two times better then a traditional renovation.

Overall cost and average carbon impact
Average over social housing stock

Total cost and carbon impact over 30 years: comparison among different retrofit approaches.
Source: Energiesprong FR, 2021

United Kingdom

Implementation date	2016-on going
Market development team	Energiesprong UK, network of 14 founding partners
Funding structure	3.6 million shared (transition Zero, H2020 2016-2019) 5.4 million shared (E=0, Interreg, 2016-2019) 11.6million shared (Mustbe0, Interreg, 2019-2022) Founding partners, both housing associations and solution providers
Achieved results	500 retrofitted houses

Energiesprong UK is an independent market development team with 14 founding partners who are frontrunners in the field of sustainability and innovation from the social housing sector as well as construction companies that share the vision of working together to innovate the sector. In addition, it has a range of supporting partners that are relevant stakeholders in the transformation Energiesprong UK is aiming to achieve. Beside the funding received by the EU projects, it is financed by the founding partners (housing associations and solution providers)¹.

Within the framework of **E = 0 Interreg project²**, two pilot projects have been delivered, both targeting single family houses:

- **In Maldon** a 5-house pilot was delivered by ENGIE (solution provider) and GSA (architect) with Moat being the housing provider. The goal was to reduce the level of carbon dioxide per house by 3.2 tonnes per year, starting from a D rating. The main challenge was that the local planning office required the street scene to remain unchanged so, apart from the addition of solar, original looks needed to be preserved. To do so, ENGIE opted for acrylic brick-effect external insulation panels, which were colour-matched to the brickwork they cover. Tenant engagement was also key for the success of the project. Tenants have been consulted throughout

the process, including weekly progress meetings, training sessions and manuals to show how to use the new technologies installed.

- **In Nottingham** 17 homes, comprising of 10 bungalows and 7 two-bedroom, three-storey houses, have been improved. They are owned by Nottingham City Homes ALMO and have been retrofitted by Melius Home. Their predecessor was the 10-home pilot project delivered by Melius Homes, designed by Studio Partington and funded by the Horizon 2020 Transition Zero projects. It won the UK Housing Award for Innovation in recognition of Nottingham City Homes’ pioneering approach to tackling energy inefficiency in older housing stock to address both climate change and fuel poverty. The positive impacts, the tenants’ satisfaction and the potential to regenerate the neighbourhood led Nottingham Councillors to support the upgrading of up to 155 homes in 2019. Therefore, the ALMO has secured over £5 million through the European Regional Development Fund with its Deep Retrofit Energy Model project, to support this rollout.

Under MustBe0 Interreg project, the focus has been shifted to multi-storey buildings pilot projects, tackling in particular: 24 units in a 2-storey building in the London Borough of Ealing and a 5-storey apartment block of 38 flats in North Kensington, London³.

Beside the demonstrators, a **MustBe0 competition was launched in 2020** by Energiesprong UK to develop new approaches for high-performance, scalable and cost-effective net zero retrofit solutions focused on apartment blocks. There were three categories to focus on: adding a layer of new dwellings on top of existing flats while ensuring whole building net zero energy, Net zero energy for low rise apartments (< 4 stories), and billing, metering and monitoring. In 2022, instead, a second design competition was launched, making £40.000 availa-

1 Energiesprong UK, 2023

2 EU Interreg NWE project E=0, 2020

3 EU Interreg NWE project MustBe0, 2023

ble for panel manufacturers and suppliers to propose offsite multi-storey fabric systems that are nearing market readiness. Competitions have been tested across different Energiesprong countries, as an effective way to collect and compare innovative solutions under development.

In conclusion, Energiesprong UK is also delivery partner (together with Turner and Townsend) of the £ 10 bn **The Retrofit Accelerator-Homes Innovation Partnership**, which is a new way to approach retrofit procurement, all across UK⁴. Indeed, in England several housing associations are public, so finding effective tendering procedures is key to the scalability of Energiesprong market. The Retrofit Accelerator - Homes programme is funded on a 50:50 basis by the Mayor of London and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). Within the partnership, seven London-based social housing providers and four UK building firms, along with a network of suppliers, are working together to stimulate a new market for whole house retrofit and reduce costs. The ultimate goal, after the three-

year Innovation Partnership, is the creation of a national framework agreement for delivering retrofit projects and exploit the Social Housing Decarbonisation Fund (SHDF). In fact, pairing social landlords with solution Providers (who are responsible for design, delivery, guaranteed performance, and in some cases maintenance), provides a runway to develop new net-zero components targeted to hit specific performance standards. In pilot projects it has been noted that procurement required suppliers to put a lot of design work, often in a short time frame. For this reason, to foster research and development, in the Innovation Partnership, bidders will receive £ 30.000 for the design stage to contribute towards costs. The main strength of the approach is that suppliers do not compete each other: if they create a solution that works within the gross maximum price, the potential market is so big that they can deliver prototypes, pilots and finally they get a spot on the national framework, which enables any UK housing provider to purchase their solutions.

Germany

Implementation date	2017-on going
Market development team	DENA, German Energy Agency
Funding structure	11.6 million shared (Must-be0, Interreg, 2019-2022) Ministry of Energy in Germany (BMWI)
Achieved results	8400 retrofitted houses

April 2017 marked the launch of the **Energiesprong initiative in Germany.**

Based on results in the Netherlands, the Ministry of Energy in Germany (BMWI) has allocated a budget to fund a market development team for the coming three years. The high level of government engagement is also demonstrated by the fact that the MDT is hosted by the **German energy agency** DENA, which is centre of expertise for energy efficiency, renewable energy sources and intelligent energy systems¹.

The first phase of market development is underway. The focus is currently on the development and scaling of solutions for smaller apartment buildings from the 1950s, 1960s and 1970s with a simple shape and high energy consumption of more than 130 kWh per square meter per year. It's estimated that there are 500,000 of these buildings in Germany a relatively large stock of similar buildings that belong to only a few housing associations. More than 80 housing companies, 16 construction companies and numerous component manufacturers are already involved in bundling demand and developing a modular system for serial renovation solutions.

Initial projects have been implemented for multi-family buildings in **Hamel, Bochum, Herford, Cologne and Mönchengladbach-Lürrip**, achieving energy savings of up to 90%. These and other ongoing projects (such as the one in **Mönchengladbach**) have been and are supported by the **EU In-**

terreg NWE Mustbe0 program and/or KFW grants, through the BEG program, according to the energy efficiency standard met².

So far 68 houses have been retrofitted and more than 500 are about to start representing an estimated construction volume of €300 million in various phases from planning to preparation. Furthermore, more than 100 construction companies are already active, and four new companies for serial refurbishment in Germany have been specifically founded. The first new factories to produce prefabricated elements are in concrete planning, and the first one will start operations shortly³.

Such numbers, together with the significant 2021 and 2023 funding programs dedicated to serial renovation (15% extra incentive if at least 80% of the facade is retrofitted with prefabricated panels), show the commitment of the German government and construction industry in shifting towards off-site manufacturing. Indeed, the first completed pilot projects demonstrate a high quality of solutions both from a technical and architectural point of view, being, so far, some of the most valuable examples of Energiesprong intervention and regeneration potential.

The project that is most worth mentioning is the one in **Mönchengladbach** where LEG, the second-largest German housing group, has launched the first Energiesprong real-world laboratory to test on a small scale what should work on a large scale. The intervention encompasses 6,000 m² of living space and 111 apartments to develop a serial renovation concept that will make it possible to renovate around 3% of the 166,000 apartments. LEG has chosen 5 solution providers (B&O, ecoworks, Fischbach, Saint-Gobain performance, and Renowate) to work on 19 identical apartment buildings from the 1950s to bring them up to the climate-neutral NetZero standard using 5 different serial renovation appro-

¹ Energiesprong DE, 2023b

² Energiesprong DE, 2023a

³ DENA, 2023

aches. The renovation was completed at the end of 2023 and the buildings achieved a huge energy leap from energy efficiency class H to A (primary energy requirements were reduced by 90%, and CO2 emissions were reduced by 570 tons per year). The fact that the buildings were identical enabled an objective comparison of the various Energiesprung approaches. The exchange between the 5 construction companies in the project was expressly desired as a central aspect of the real-world laboratory. Indeed, the knowledge gained is helping to find scalable solutions more quickly.

Finally, another strong indicator of the interest of the German market in industrialization was the foundation of the company Renowate GmbH in April 2022. It is a joint venture between the hou-

sing company LEG and the Austrian construction group Rhomberg. The start-up is a total solutions provider that offers complete energy renovation from the initial diagnosis to turnkey installation. As a cross-industry joint venture, Renowate combines housing expertise with construction experience to develop a scalable renovation solution that makes it possible to decarbonize large housing stocks quickly and cost-effectively. A special feature characterizing Renowate projects is the use of the self-developed tenant communication IT platform. The aim is to provide tenants with all relevant and transparent information before, during, and after the intervention, allowing the property owner to save personnel capacity previously used for time-consuming tenant communication and complaints handling.

Italy

Implementation date	2021-on going
Market development team	EDERA, social enterprise for the renovation and decarbonisation of the built environment
Funding structure	Fondazione Cariplo The solution providers involved in the different supply chains
Achieved results	1100 retrofitted houses

Energiesprong Italy was established in March 2021 following an initial activation phase led by Habitech and REbuild. **EDERA Srl** Impresa Sociale was founded by REDO SGR S.p.A., Benefit Corporation, FHS – Fondazione Housing Sociale, ANCE – National Association of Builders, and Thomas Miorin. It is an innovation centre focused on decarbonising and retrofitting buildings.

EDERA set up a team of 20 to adapt the Energiesprong approach to Italy. The team’s role is to encourage collaboration and innovation in the supply chain. EDERA also works with a **network of experts** to address emerging barriers (e.g. market potential, business models, procurement processes, stock clustering, tenant engagement). The market development team has received financial support from **Fondazione Cariplo**, a prominent philanthropic institution. Moreover, the solution providers who join the network are required to pay an annual fee since they recognize the value of the open innovation program.

To date, Energiesprong Italy counts:

- **50 solution providers, construction companies and design studios** are involved in the movement and have innovated production. Multiple supply chains have been established to undertake pilot projects. These are Italy’s first examples of deep industrial retrofits using different technologies and structural materials (wood, steel, concrete and hybrid couplings).
- **15 social housing organisations**, divided between local public bodies, FEDERCASA members and private cooperatives, which own or manage over

150,000 homes. Meetings and workshops have been organised to understand their needs and how the supply can provide appropriate solutions.

- **9 pilot buildings** for a total of around 1100 apartments retrofitted with offsite integrated components.

More in detail, in July 2022 the first pilot project was launched in **Corte Franca** (Lombardy region). Differently from other Energiesprong countries, it was a private building realized by Woodbeton, a major panel manufacturer and general contractor, part of the Italian Energiesprong network. This choice has been forced by boundary conditions: 110% incentives have doped the renovation market, creating a surplus of private renovation demand which made public and social stock less urgent and less appealing.

A second private pilot project occurred in 2024 in **Pieve Emanuele** (Lombardy) and it used around 2000 light offsite façade panels, produced by Iso-pan, for energy and seismic retrofitting of 6 big condominiums in 3 months.

With the end of the 110% incentive and the forthcoming PNRR action line encouraging public intervention, the private sector became less attractive. For this reason, a pipeline of buildings from the public and cooperative housing sector was selected. These buildings are in urgent need of energy efficiency and energy poverty reduction. This is the case of **Via Russoli**, a set of 4 public residential towers in Milan, for a total of 187 dwellings. Achievements include the use of innovative offsite facades for energy retrofitting made with rice hulk biobased insulation, and the application of photovoltaic panels to meet energy needs and reduced energy poverty. Furthermore, a very interesting tenant engagement process was activated with the inhabitants, and it led to shared roof gardens.

Public organizations are increasingly aware of the need for alternative and innovative models to effi-

ciently manage their stock due to limited financial capacity. Indeed, in Via Russoli a Public Private Partnership was implemented for the first time: Woodbeton, Ricehouse and a2a joined forces to candidate to the bid proposing an **EPC+ (Energy Performance Contract including energy supply and the maintenance of both technical and envelope systems)**.

Overall, strengths that characterize Energiesprong in Italy include the introduction of **anti-seismic improvement elements**, which require special attention at the design and structural level, and the **integration of plant systems** for summer cooling, given that insulation alone is insufficient in southern Europe. These elements make the model suitable for the Italian context and enrich the catalogue of technological solutions available internationally. Indeed, in 2024 in the context of e-SAFE H2020 project, the first intervention in public social housing in south Italy was carried out in **Catania**, Sicily, a region characterized by high summer temperatures. The high levels of efficiency achieved have de-

monstrated the adaptability and versatility of these instruments in different climatic areas.

All the projects demonstrate the feasibility of key Energiesprong requirements:

- Achieved NZEB energy performance, reducing non-renewable energy consumption;
- Improved anti-seismic performance, increasing the vulnerability index;
- Minimized inconvenience to residents by installing façade panels without scaffolding;
- Enabled fully electric buildings with integrated with PV systems and heat pumps for DHW production;
- Significantly reduced environmental impact with respect to traditional interventions.

Finally, another challenge that Energiesprong Italy intends to tackle in the near future is to ensure high standards of quality to retrofit and preserve the nation's **architectural heritage** ensuring a high variety of finishings, materials and elements typologies adaptable to the broad Italian building stock.

Refurbished building in Corte Franca (Lombardy)

3.3 The IDR business model

This paragraph explores – both quantitatively and qualitatively – business models emerged from Energiesprong and H2020 INFINITE studies around the economic convenience of offsite and industrialized retrofits.

Energiesprong Italy and the total cost of ownership approach

As it emerges from previous sections, each country that adopted the Energiesprong approach has developed it according to the specific characteristics and opportunities of its local context, demonstrating—through the first pilot projects—the technical feasibility of the interventions using off-site solutions. The greatest challenge therefore remains its economic sustainability, as highlighted by several studies on the topic. France, Germany, and Italy have conducted independent analyses with the aim of comparing, in a structured and transparent manner, deep, industrialized, and integrated retrofit interventions—typical of the Energiesprong approach—with traditional solutions, while simultaneously capturing the technical, economic, and social benefits of the former.

Below is a detailed analysis of the Italian case. The assumptions regarding economies of scale are drawn on data from France and Germany, since these two countries have already entered the scale-up phase, offering a benchmarking opportunity that is still absent in Italy.

As anticipated in the introduction, the study is based on the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) model, evaluating—over a 30-year horizon—the entire lifecycle of costs and revenues associated with the building: from the initial retrofit to energy consumption, from management and maintenance to financial charges, incentives, and rental income. The TCO framework makes it possible to consider not only immediately

monetizable aspects but also the less visible ones—environmental, social, climatic, and seismic—that emerge from a long-term perspective.

To construct a robust model suitable for different contexts, the study analyzed the actors involved in the retrofit process, along with their contractual models and the resulting financial flows. The model was then validated through five simulations on real cases, differing in size and technological solutions adopted but sharing the same energy and/or seismic performance levels. The consistency of the results allowed for the identification of significant trends.

The study adopts the EPC+ contractual model as a reference—an evolution of the traditional Energy Performance Contract (EPC)—which involves the participation of Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) to enable the integration of services offered to the building owner.

In traditional models, the property owner must manage separate contracts for energy supply, maintenance, efficiency upgrades, and operational services, resulting in management complexity (see image in the next page on the left). The EPC model simplifies this structure: the ESCo carries out energy efficiency measures advancing the related costs, guarantees energy performance, and is remunerated through a fee linked to the savings achieved. However, building envelope maintenance remains outside the contractual scope.

The EPC+ model adopted in the study expands this approach by also including maintenance of the refurbished envelope for the full duration of the contract, making the ESCo the sole point of contact for the client (see image below on the right). The beneficiary therefore receives the retrofit without upfront capital and benefits from continuous oversight of the building’s performance, ensuring efficiency and quality. This generates a natural alignment of incentives: both parties benefit from the actual energy savings achieved.

Thanks to this service integration, EPC+ is fully consistent with Energiesprong logic, which aims to reduce disruptions for inhabitants and simplify processes for property owners. Initial comparisons between traditional technologies (BAU) and Energiesprong offsite solutions (ES) reveal that the latter offer direct and indirect advantages, thanks to industrial production with numerically controlled machinery. These factors result in direct impacts on major cost items and reduced indirect costs, due to scaffold-free installations, increased safety, and lower operational risks. The five real-case simulations show that the initial retrofit cost (CAPEX) for ES is slightly higher (+2%

to +10%), but subsequent savings (OPEX) are significant:

- **25% reduction in maintenance,**
- **40% reduction in financial charges,**
- **4% reduction in management costs,**
- **50% reduction in energy consumption compared to the baseline.**

In the medium term, total costs for Energiesprong and BAU become comparable both in the baseline scenario—with payments made to different suppliers according to renovation progress (see the first image on the next page)—and in the EPC+ scenario, typically characterized in Italy by a fee distributed over 10 years, with the possibility of extension (see the second image on the next page). In the long term, Energiesprong achieves an economic advantage of 2% to 5%, while, relative to the status before the retrofit, the cumulative balance improves by 50%. For tenants, the total post-retrofit cost (rent + energy + management + maintenance) increases only moderately—up to 16% compared to the existing condition—remaining similar between ES and BAU solutions.

3. IDR Best Practices

Future trends from Energiesprong France and Germany

To move from first projects to medium perspective, a third scenario was assessed, considering a conservative cost-reduction. This is because operators involved in Energiesprong projects currently apply higher margins, due to the adoption of new processes, technologies, contractual models, and organizational structures, which carry greater investment risks.

Nevertheless, these innovations have strong optimization potential thanks to the industrial nature of the process and the economies of scale enabled by increasing intervention volumes. In this regard, two main levels of cost reduction were identified:

1. Increased and optimized production volumes:

As more industrial panels and components are produced, the unit cost decreases, thanks to the distribution of fixed costs over a larger number of units and improved production efficiency. Higher volumes also support further investments in automation, optimizing the entire production chain. In countries where Energiesprong has already been implemented on scale, this has led to significant reductions in overall retrofit costs within a few years.

2. Learning curve effects: The progressive diffusion of the industrialized approach allows optimization of operational and management procedures, thanks to growing acquired skills,

generating further reductions in management and maintenance costs over time.

Several studies have quantified the savings achieved in France and Germany due to economies of scale and learning curves.

A first study— *“Is the Energy Transition of Housing Financially Viable? Unlocking the Potential of Deep Retrofits with New Business Models 1”* by Ezio Micelli, Giulia Giliberto, and Eleonora Righetto (2025)— shows that deep energy retrofits are currently not financially viable: a typical 70 m² intervention costs about €115,000 (1,568–1,624 €/m²), while economic benefits do not offset the initial expenditure. As a result, net present values are negative, requiring public support of 50–60% for private owners and up to 65% for developers in weaker markets, such as social housing.

Using updated 2023 data from French projects, the Energiesprong model could change this scenario from a long-term perspective (see fig.5): offsite production and industrialization could reduce retrofit costs from €1,400/m² to around €500/m², making interventions sustainable even without subsidies, especially in urban contexts with higher property values. The study also highlights significant territorial variability in economic feasibility and the need for tailored policies for both demand and the innovative supply chain.

¹ <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/15/7/1175>

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Fig. 5: Cost reduction of offsite renovations, based on actualized French data; from *Is the Energy Transition of Housing Financially Viable? Unlocking the Potential of Deep Retrofits with New Business Models* ¹ by Ezio Micelli, Giulia Giliberto, and Eleonora Righetto (2025)

In the **MASH Grand Ouest** ² program— a major French initiative in the Pays de la Loire region involving the retrofit of 762 social housing units—the application of the Energiesprong model demonstrated how scaling up and industrialization can significantly reduce retrofit costs. Compared to early French multi-family housing projects, CAPEX reductions were substantial (see the image on the next page above): –33% in Lot 4 and –48% in Lot 5, thanks to standardized prefabricated timber façades, consistent energy module types, lean construction methods, and accumulated production/installation expertise. Large-scale interventions allowed design and R&D costs to be amortized, strengthened the local industrial supply chain, and reduced installation times, with shorter and more predictable construction phases.

The report also notes that these reductions are not final: better knowledge of the building stock, more targeted selection of suitable buildings for offsite retrofit, and the simplification of technical solutions are expected to yield further cost decreases in future project waves.

The MASH experience shows that deep collective-housing retrofits can rapidly benefit from multiple learning curves, moving towards a more competitive and replicable economic model.

Finally, the German Energiesprong program ³ 4 clearly shows how serial renovation is benefiting from economies of scale. According to recent publications, projects completed before 2023 often exceeded €2,400/m², while those initiated from 2023 onward frequently fall below €1,650/m², meaning a 30–35% reduction (see the image on the next page below). This decrease is attributed to growing market maturity, solution standardization, and enriched know-how, supported by 17,000 retrofitted units. In addition, larger interventions—over 50 dwellings—are up to €500/m² cheaper than smaller projects. Completion times also improve due to learning effects: prefabrication and more experienced teams have reduced the duration and variability seen in early pilot projects.

Overall, serial renovation is entering a phase of greater reliability and cost-effectiveness, driven by increased volumes and accumulated sector expertise.

1 <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/15/7/1175>

2 https://www.novabuild.fr/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/Rex_mash_partie_1_FR.pdf

3 <https://www.dena.de/en/projects/Energiesprong-deutschland/>

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In addition to cost reductions, the growing number of projects enables further energy optimization, thanks to better alignment between energy diagnoses and real consumptions, as well as sophisticated monitoring systems that reduce waste during the use phase.

Based on these considerations, the advanced scenario introduces additional cost reductions relative to the baseline:

- Retrofit intervention: –20%
- Routine maintenance: –5%

- Management: –5%
- Energy: –5%

When these optimizations are compared to baseline scenario results, the economic advantage of Energiesprong over BAU solutions can increase substantially, reaching a **10–20% positive differential in the 30-year TCO**. The resulting economic curves—illustrated in fig. 8—confirm a trajectory of continuous improvement for industrialized solutions, consolidating the offsite approach as one of the most effective strategies to accelerate the transformation of national building stocks.

Revenues and expenditures of traditionally procured renovation including Economies of scale; from MODELLO ECONOMICO Energiesprong v.1.0 by EDERA s.r.l. Impresa Sociale

INFINITE and the flexible combination of industrialized envelope kits

While Energiesprong has demonstrated the technical and economic feasibility of an integrated retrofit approach (intervening simultaneously on opaque and transparent envelope components and building systems), the H2020 INFINITE project expands this scope, introducing three business models designed to support the adoption of different kits for Industrialized Deep Renovation (see page “[About the project](#)” for details).

The three models—explained in the report available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16941900>—are based on a central idea: offsite retrofit solutions are effective only if they are combined and packaged into different offerings depending on the type of client, since each market actor has

different objectives, financial constraints, decision-making capacities, and value levers.

This model integrates an industrialized passive roof, rooftop photovoltaics panels (BIPV), smart windows, and smart energy management systems (aBMS), as represented in fig. 9. It is designed for condominiums, enabling targeted interventions on private or semi-private components, generating self-production of energy, bill savings, and aesthetic improvements. It can be financed directly by owners or through ESCOs or utilities, which recover the investment via energy savings and periodic fixed fees. Integration with Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) can increase profitability.

1. Model for private collective users

This model integrates an industrialized passive roof, rooftop photovoltaics panels (BIPV), smart windows, and smart energy management systems (aBMS), as represented in fig. 9. It is designed for condominiums, enabling targeted interventions on private or semi-private components, generating self-production of energy, bill savings, and aesthetic improvements. It can be financed directly by owners or through ESCOs or utilities, which recover the investment via energy savings and periodic fixed fees. Integration with Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) can increase profitability.

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2. Model for public social housing providers

This model — the closest to Energiesprong — combines prefabricated passive façades, BIPV, solar thermal (BIST), ventilation & fresh air systems, heat pumps, and aBMS, as represented in fig. 10. Intended for public entities managing large building stocks, it aims to maximize site efficiency, reduce construction times, control costs, and guarantee performance. Indeed off-site integration lowers risks, change orders, and disturbances for tenants. Given limited financial capacity, the model is well suited to tools such as **Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) with EPC contracts**, in which the initial capex is covered by the ESCo and the Public Administration can split payments over time.

3. Model for Real Estate developers and investors

The third model integrates passive prefabricated envelopes with façade and/or green-roof modules, as well as BIPV and aBMS, as represented in fig. 11. It targets developers and investment funds oriented toward ESG objectives. The key feature is the high environmental and aesthetic value: integrated greenery enhances architectural quality, comfort, and climatic performance, increasing market attractiveness. This model can boost asset value, obtain better financing conditions and green certifications, and in some cases include prefabricated volumetric extensions (new rooftop spaces) as an additional revenue source.

Conclusion

Industrialized retrofit solutions — whether highly integrated like Energiesprong or modular and flexible like INFINITE— are demonstrating increasing technical and economic feasibility. Among the various business models tested, EPC+

appears the most promising, as it eliminates upfront investment for owners and guarantees medium- to long-term energy performance, contributing to the tangible reduction of emissions in the renovated building.

3.4 EU funded research projects

To meet the European Union’s energy transition targets, especially after the ongoing revision of the EPBD, EED, and RED directives, the building environment is expected to change significantly over the next few decades¹. However, energy renovations are expensive, and owners or building managers often lack the means to finance them. To fill the large financial gaps, several funding streams are available at the EU level to ensure that the necessary investments are made on the required scale. In fact, as stated in the Renovation Wave, “the EU’s reconstruction instrument, NextGenerationEU, together with the EU’s multiannual financial framework, will provide an unprecedented volume of resources that can also be used to kick-start renovation for reconstruction, resilience, and greater social inclusion”.

The infographic below provides an overview of the EU funding schemes (from Renovate Europe), under three main headings:

- Supporting **direct investment** in quality construction and energy efficiency;
- **Leveraging private investment** on a larger scale and funding technical support services;
- Stimulating **research and innovation** and removing market barriers to building renovation.

Direct investment projects are primarily supported by the **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)**, the **Cohesion Fund (CF)** and the **Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)**. These funds aim to strengthen economic, social, and territorial cohesion by correcting imbalances between regions. Projects include investments in regional and urban

development, infrastructure improvements, and initiatives to enhance energy efficiency in buildings².

Interreg is a program that promotes European territorial cooperation. Funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), Interreg supports cross-border, transnational, and interregional projects that aim to solve common problems among European regions and countries. These projects can cover various sectors, including the environment, innovation, sustainable mobility, and urban development. Interreg facilitates the sharing of knowledge and best practices, contributing to strengthening the economic, social, and territorial cohesion of the EU.

The **InvestEU Programme** is a key initiative for **leveraging private investment**. With an EU budget guarantee of €26.2 billion, the InvestEU Fund aims to mobilize more than €372 billion in additional investment by backing the investments of financial partners such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) Group. This program supports projects in areas like green and digital transitions, innovation, and social investments, thereby crowding in private investors to achieve significant economic and environmental impacts^{3 4}.

Finally, the third point on research and innovation the third point includes Horizon and LIFE projects, which provide around €17 billion for energy efficiency-related research. In total, more than €100 billion will be made available, which is around 20% of the EU budget that the European Green Deal Investment Plan has earmarked for achieving the 2030 climate-related targets⁵.

1 https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en

2 https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes_en

3 https://investeu.europa.eu/investeu-programme_en

4 https://investeu.europa.eu/investeu-programme/investeu-fund/frequently-asked-questions-about-investeu-fund_en

5 https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/renovation-wave_en

The **Horizon** program is one of the main initiatives of the European Union to fund research and innovation. Horizon 2020 (2014-2020) and Horizon Europe (2021-2027) were designed to address global challenges, promote industrial competitiveness, and improve the quality of life for European citizens. Horizon funds are allocated to projects ranging from basic research to technological innovation, with a strong focus on environmental sustainability and climate neutrality. These projects include the development of advanced technologies for building renovation, the use of renewable energy sources, and the implementation of digital tools such as Building Information Modeling (BIM)⁶.

The **LIFE** program is dedicated to the environment and climate action. Funded by the European Commission, LIFE supports projects that contribute to the transition towards a sustainable, circular, resource-efficient, and low-carbon economy. The

LIFE Clean Energy Transition program (2021-2027) is a specific subsection aimed at facilitating the clean energy transition by funding projects that promote energy efficiency, the use of renewable energy, and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions⁷.

Research and innovation funded by these programs have led to the development of advanced technologies for industrialized building renovation, such as integrated timber façade panels, advanced HVAC components, and technologies for harvesting renewable energy. These projects address sustainable financial and operational models to facilitate the market adoption of such innovations.

In summary, the European Commission’s 2021 to 2027 active funds through the Horizon, LIFE, and Interreg initiatives play a crucial role in promoting research, innovation, and sustainability, contributing to achieving climate neutrality and the intermediate targets for 2030.

Summary of funding allocated by the EU for energy efficiency of buildings between 2021 and 2027

6 <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/growth/items/690437/en>

7 https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/eu_renovation_wave_strategy_0.pdf

Horizon projects

Of the **Interreg, LIFE and Horizon programmes** mentioned above, the analysis in this Outlook focuses on the latter, which funds a wide range of activities, including scientific research, technological development, industrial innovation and business take-up.

The main **H2020** and **Horizon Europe** projects on industrialised deep renovation have been evaluated in order to highlight those that implement innovation in real **pilot buildings** (one of the most recurrent requirements in the Horizon call for proposals), which is the first step towards market activation of IDR (the countries falling into this category are shown in yellow on the map on page 39).

The analysis of these projects shows that they favour the use of **industrially prefabricated panels** (60%) as an energy efficiency solution, especially the most recent programmes. These panels significantly reduce the energy consumption of buildings, while using durable and quick to install solutions and offer a high level of comfort. These panels also enable integrated solutions such as **photovoltaic** (38%) or **solar thermal** (21%) systems, ensuring the use of renewable energy to power high-efficiency

machines for heating/cooling, mechanical ventilation or domestic hot water (**HVAC**, 29%). These technologies can ensure even better performance when implemented with **BEM** and **BMS** systems (29%). Finally, the design phase can be optimised and more efficient through the use of **BIM** methods (31%), which are also useful during the intervention phase and throughout the building life cycle.

It is also essential to identify **business models** (24%) that ensure the creation of a stable market aimed at increasing the profitability and sustainability of this type of intervention from an economic and a social point of view.

In conclusion, many initiatives spread across Europe address industrialised deep renovation from different perspectives, using and focusing on different innovations. Most of them have been initiated and developed thanks to EU and national funding, while Energiesprong is the first autonomous movement. Even if cost compression and scalability are still open challenges, the forthcoming library of case studies shows the variability, architectural quality and high performance that IDR solutions can bring to the built environment.

	Program	Start	End	Project coordinator	Integrated solutions	Prefabricated facade	Prefabricated roof	PV panels	Solar thermal panels	Smart window	Systems (HVAC)	BMS	BIM	Digital Platform	Business Model	PILOTS 1	PILOTS 2	PILOTS 3	PILOTS 4	PILOTS 5	
1	4Rin EU	Horizon 2020	2016	2021	IT	x					x				x	SP	NL	NO	IT		
2	ABRACADABRA	Horizon 2020	2016	2019	IT	x	x	x		x	x				x						
3	BERTIM	Horizon 2020	2015	2019	SP	x				x	x		x			SP	FR	SE			
4	BRESAER	Horizon 2020	2015	2019	SP	x	x		x	x	x				x	SP					
5	BE-SMART	Horizon 2020	2018	2022	CH			x													
6	BuiltHEAT	Horizon 2020	2015	2020	IT	x					x										
7	Drive 0	Horizon 2020	2019	2023	NL								x			IT	EE	LT			
8	E2VENT	Horizon 2020	2015	2018	FR	x					x	x				SP	FR	PO			
10	ENSNARE	Horizon 2020	2021	2025	SP	x		x	x	x		x	x	x		EE	BG	IT			
11	IMPRESS	Horizon 2020	2015	2018	NO		x						x		x	RO					
12	INCUBE	Horizon Europe	2022	2026	EL	x		x	x				x		x	SP	NL	IT			
13	INFINITE	Horizon 2020	2020	2026	IT	x	x				x	x	x	x	x	FR	SI	IT			
14	INSITER	Horizon 2020	2014	2018	NL								x								
15	INSUPanel	Horizon 2020	2017	2020	SP		x														
16	MORE CONNECT	Horizon 2020	2014	2019	NL	x	x	x					x			EE	PT	LV			
17	OptEEmal	Horizon 2020	2015	2019	SP									x							
18	OutPHit	Horizon 2020	2020	2024	DE		x								x	AT	DE	EL			
19	P2Endure	Horizon 2020	2016	2021	NL		x						x			PO	NL	NO			
20	PLUG-N-HARVEST	Horizon 2020	2017	2022	GR		x									SP	DE	EL			
21	PLURAL	Horizon 2020	2020	2024	GR	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x	CZ	SP	EL			
22	POWERSKINPLUS	Horizon 2020	2019	2024	PO	x	x		x							PT	DE	CZ			
24	REHOUSE	Horizon 2022	2022	2026	SP	x	x		x		x					FR	IT	HU	EL		
26	PRO-GET-ONE	Horizon 2020	2017	2022	IT	x					x					NL	IT	RO			
27	RE4	Horizon 2020	2016	2020	IT										x	UK	SP	IT			
28	REMODULES	Horizon 2020	2020	2024	NL										x						
29	RE-SKIN	Horizon 2020	2017	2022	SP	x	x					x				FR	IT	BG			
30	REZBUILD	Horizon 2020	2017	2020	IT								x		x	NO	SP	IT			
31	StepUP	Horizon 2020	2019	2024	UK	x	x									HU	SP				
33	TransitionZero	Horizon 2020	2016	2018	UK		x														
34	e-SAFE	Horizon 2020	2020	2025	IT	x	x		x	x		x									
35	Envision	Horizon 2020	2017	2022	NL	x	x		x	x	x					NL					
36	Excess	Horizon 2020	2019	2024	AT			x	x							AT	BE	FI	SP		
37	Fortesie	Horizon Europe	2022	2025	LU	x	x	x	x		x	x				EL	PT	PO	LV		
38	Green instruct	Horizon 2020	2016	2020	UK	x	x														
39	Heart	Horizon 2020	2017	2022	IT		x		x			x				IT	FR				
40	Heart4cool	Horizon 2020	2016	2021	IT			x	x		x										
41	InnoWEE	Horizon 2020	2016	2020	IT		x														
42	Inperso	Horizon Europe	2022	2026	SP		x				x		x			SP	NL	EL			
44	Reco2st	Horizon 2020	2018	2021	DK			x		x	x	x									
45	RenoZEB	Horizon 2020	2017	2022	SP		x														
46	Rinno	Horizon 2020	2020	2025	IT		x		x		x		x	x	x	FR	EL	PO	DK		
47	Surefit	Horizon 2020	2020	2025	PT			x	x		x					PT	UK	EL	SP	FI	
	Totale					34%	53%	4%	34%	19%	15%	26%	17%	28%	9%	21%					

4.

Case studies

KEY TAKEAWAYS BOX

- The 26 case studies collected across 7 European countries confirm that IDR is technically feasible across a wide range of building typologies — from 1950s terraced houses to 12-storey social housing towers — and climatic contexts.
- Offsite façade panels dominate as the primary technical lever, frequently integrating windows, photovoltaic systems, ventilation ducts, and in some cases solar thermal panels — enabling simultaneous envelope insulation and energy system upgrade in a single intervention.
- Projects consistently achieve post-renovation energy consumptions between 15 and 90 kWh/m²/year, with the majority of Energiesprong cases targeting net-zero energy (E=0) over guaranteed performance periods of 20–30 years.
- A trend analysis of 74 solutions across 8 countries reveals that timber-frame panels lead the European market (68% of solutions), followed by light steel frame (18%). France (20 solutions) and Germany (16 solutions) are the most mature markets; Italy (19 solutions) shows the widest technological diversity, driven in part by the additional need for seismic performance in its building stock.
- 47% of assessed solutions have been applied to real projects, of which 30% are market-competitive; The large share of solutions never yet pilot-tested (21%) signals the sector's active R&D investment.
- Timber frame solutions produce larger, heavier panels (71 kg/m² on average) with faster on-site installation (180 m²/day), while light steel frame solutions offer lighter, more flexible modules (56 kg/m², 134 m²/day) better suited to complex or irregular building geometries.
- The gap between current deployment and the renovation scale required by EU targets remains significant. Closing it will require offsite solutions to move from promising pilots to mainstream practice — a transition that demands sustained R&D, cost competitiveness, stronger value chains, and regulatory frameworks that systematically recognize and reward industrialized renovation.

Introduction

The transformation of the building renovation market requires not only innovative technical solutions, but also concrete demonstration of their applicability, effectiveness, and replicability. The case studies collected in this chapter represent the most tangible evidence of that transformation: real interventions, in existing buildings, that put different IDR models to the test and demonstrate their potential across a variety of contexts, typologies, and national settings.

These projects are not simply construction sites — they are living laboratories of innovation. Each case study is the result of a collaborative process involving public and private clients, contractors, designers, researchers, and solution providers, with the shared objective of testing different approaches, each excellent in its own way. Some originate from the Energiesprong movement, which has driven the most systematic and widely replicated industrialized renovation model in Europe. Others have been developed within the framework of EU-funded Horizon research projects, including INFINITE, or through independent national programs and pioneering private initiatives. Together, they reflect the breadth and diversity of the IDR landscape across Europe today.

The variety of approaches presented here reflects both the richness of Europe's existing building stock and the flexibility of industrialized renovation models in responding to different performance requirements, regulatory environments, climatic conditions, and client needs — from small, terraced houses to large multi-storey social housing towers, from Western Europe's timber-dominated markets to Italy's seismically complex territories.

It should be noted that the 26 case studies included in this chapter represent a curated selection of particularly relevant and illustrative examples — they are not exhaustive. Many more projects are underway or completed across Europe, as the IDR landscape is a living laboratory that is evolving rapidly. For a continuously updated and more comprehensive repository of industrialized deep renovation projects and the solutions connected to them, it's possible to visit the **Industrialized Deep Retrofit Hub** at <https://energyefficientbuilding.eurac.edu/en/reno-hub/>, where case studies are described by existing building characteristics, energy renovation concept, technology solution sets, design and installation phases, performance and savings, cultural and climatic aspects.

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Kapfenberg

The lead project pursues the goal of highly efficient refurbishment of existing buildings and housing estates in urban areas. The main focus is on buildings constructed between 1950 and 1980. The project is divided into 5 sub-projects, which cover all aspects of the high-quality refurbishment of residential buildings, from basic research to final monitoring.

The objectives of the implementation project (Kapfenberg) were to reduce the heating requirement and achieve the plus-energy standard by converting the energy supply to district heating, solar thermal energy, heat pumps and photovoltaics. The façade was renovated using prefabricated vertical timber elements that are used as a new insulation level and as building services shafts. For research purposes, 16 residential units were equipped with ventilation with heat recovery and the other 16 with an exhaust air system and exhaust air/water heat pump solution.

General Data	
Address	Johann-Böhm-Straße 34, 8605 Bruck an der Mur
Year of renovation	2012-2014 (Planning 2011)
Housing owner	Residential building group ENNSTAL
General contractor	Nussmüller Architekten ZT GmbH
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1960s
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	4
Number of dwellings	reduced from 48 to 32
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	2270m ²
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	Solid structure
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ² a)	165 kwh/m ² a

Retrofit information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process?	No
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	Yes, demolished and discharged to the ground
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wooden support frame, 30cm,
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to the existing facade and the main load is transferred via a console
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	District heating network
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Solar thermal panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Yes (building service shafts)
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, exhaust air heat pump
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	4.2 Mio.
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	15 kwh/m ² a
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	plus energy attempt; 120,000 kilowatt hours annually
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	Facade integration of renewable energies is costly, Costs quickly escalate with prefabrication, Ventilation and heat pumps in combination with storage AND district heating are difficult to manage.

AEE Intec

AEE Intec

Angers

This project is taking place in Angers. More precisely, it is taking place at 1 to 52 Rue d'Auvergne and 3 to 13 Rue Maurice Suard 49 100 Angers. The operation of the lessor Podeliha is a demonstrator project, in advance of phase, of the collective MASH approach. It involves the Energiesprong renovation of 32 semi-detached houses in R+1. These houses have an average surface area of 86m². They include the following typologies: 9T4, 18T5 and 5T6.

This operation is a demonstrator project of the collective MASH approach. This approach brings together 14 lessors from the Pays de la Loire and Brittany region for the renovation of more than 2000 homes.

General Data	
Address	Rue d'Auvergne
Year of renovation	2021
Housing owner	Podeliha
General contractor	Bouygues Construction
Panel manufacturer	Bouygues Construction

Building information	
Year of construction	1969
Number of buildings	32
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	32
Balconies	No
Total living area (m2)	2,750 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Individual gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	183

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	1969
Volume increase	32
Scaffoldings	2
Inhabited during renovation	32
Tenant engagement process	No
Total onsite works duration (days)	2,750 m ²
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies	Classic concrete structure
Facade installation time (m2/day)	Individual gaz
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	183
Panel weight handling	Hanged to existing facades
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Wood only for structure
Photovoltaic panels	No
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	No need to change windows
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system	No
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	120
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	0%
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	No
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Halluin

The Bouvier residence, located in Halluin, in Hauts-de-France, is currently being renovated using the Energiesprong method. This 80-unit residence will be transformed into two residences of 40 and 30 residences. The project began in March 2022 and is scheduled for delivery in 2023.

The project involves the renovation of 40 Must-Be0 and 30 Massiréno homes. The project began in March 2022 and is scheduled for delivery in 2023.

The residence was no longer adapted to current standards and needed a complete renovation. The Energiesprong method proved to be the solution of choice for undertaking this comprehensive work. Indeed, the objective is to improve the energy performance of the building, but also to improve its comfort. Building extensions, green spaces and energy comfort are just three examples.

General Data	
Address	Résidence Bouvier
Year of renovation	2022-2023
Housing owner	Notre Logis
General contractor	Tommasini
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1966
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	-
Number of dwellings	40
Balconies	Loggias
Total living area (m2)	2,000 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	Individual gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	385

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	Yes
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	No, dwellings were empty when renovation occurred
Tenant engagement process	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	0%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies	Yes, demolished and hanged to new facade
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Traditionnal ext insulation
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels	Yes
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	60
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E=0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	30 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Hem, Lille

Located in the north of France and constructed in 1950, this twin home features two attached residences with a total heated floor area of approximately 84 square meters. With a combined overall façade area of 111 square meters (including windows and doors) and 88 square meters without, the building offers a compact yet versatile space for renovation experimentation. The two-storey building has a garden space in front and at the back, and the two residences have a common wall and a pitched roof. Bricks masonry perimeter walls surround the building. Situated within a neighbourhood of 207 dwellings undergoing an Energiesprong renovation program, this building is part of a larger initiative to enhance energy efficiency and sustainability in the community by 2025.

As part of H2020 INFINITE project, the all-industrialised BIPV kit will be installed on the façades. The possibility of installing PV for the roof has also been studied. Building façade will receive exterior insulation, replacement of window and French door systems, and replacing the roofing (except the structure). The heat pumps and the electrical connections will also be upgraded and updated.

General Data	
Address	Hem, Lille
Year of renovation	2025
Housing owner	Vilogia
General contractor	BYCN
Panel manufacturer	Sunage

Building information	
Year of construction	1950
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	2
Balconies?	no
Total living area (m2)	168 or 162 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	88 m ²
Roof surface (m2)	50 m ²
Type of structure	Brick

Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Gas boiler
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	273 kWh/ m ²

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	-
Volume increase	no
Scaffoldings	no
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	65%
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	no
Facade installation time (m2/ day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wooden facade panels
Panel weight handling (ex. changed to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Grass wool Isolant "Gramitherm"
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Solar thermal panels?	no
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel?	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	YES, on the ground floor
Monitoring system?	yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	target of 86 kWh/m ²
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	all E= 0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

MASH Lot 1

In three municipalities of Maine et Loire (49), 4 mass renovation operations were carried out on a complex of 50 housing units.

The operations are as follows:

- Change of ventilation and heating system: Installation of a Nilan tower (Heating, DHW and double-flow ventilation);
- Renovation of the envelope with exterior insulation: prefabricated panels in the factory by Sogea (wood wool, FOB) and traditional ITE;
- Insulation of the attic;
- Installation of photovoltaic panels.

Energy efficiency is guaranteed for 30 years thanks to the installations installed in the buildings.

General Data	
Address	Many cities in Pays de la Loire
Year of renovation	2023
Housing owner	Maine & Loire Habitat
General contractor	Sogea Atlantique (Vinci)
Panel manufacturer	Sogea Atlantique (Vinci)

Building information	
Year of construction	1960-80
Number of buildings	342
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	342
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	23,600 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	Electric heating
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	154

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	None
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	50-60%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Metal - Large panels - With glazing
Panel weight handling	Hanged to existing facades
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Insulation in wood
Photovoltaic panels	Yes
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes - Internal module
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	60
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E=0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	30 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

MASH Lot 5

This project is part of the MASH initiative (Mutualisation d'Achat au Service de l'Habitat), an Energiesprong renovation purchasing center, aimed at massifying high-performance energy renovations through group orders.

This lot stands out from previous Energiesprong contracts due to the typology of buildings it involves: Sarthe Habitat chose this approach to renovate an 11-storey tower comprising 251 housing units, located in the heart of Le Mans. This tower represents a particular challenge due to its size and location. The renovation work on this emblematic project was launched on Monday, May 22, 2023.

This initiative demonstrates Sarthe Habitat's commitment to improving the energy efficiency of housing, even in complex buildings such as residential towers. Using the Energiesprong approach, Sarthe Habitat aims to transform this tower into a zero-energy building, thus offering better comfort to residents, sustainable protection against rising energy prices (energy shield) while radically reducing its environmental impact. This pilot project will contribute to the learning and dissemination of good practices in high-performance energy renovation, while serving as a model for future similar projects.

General Data	
Address	Résidence George Gauthier
Year of renovation	2024
Housing owner	Sarthe Habitat
General contractor	Groupe Altyn
Panel manufacturer	LCA/Ossabois

Building information	
Year of construction	1975
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	12
Number of dwellings	251
Balconies	No
Total living area (m2)	14,500
Facade surface (m2)	-

Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	Collective gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process?	
Total onsite works duration (days)	
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wood - Large panels - With glazing
Panel weight handling	Hanged to existing facades
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Wood for facades
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	90
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E=0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	30 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	

Raismes

The Anne Godeau elementary school welcomes 171 students. It is located in Raismes, in Hauts-de-France. It was built in 1967. The City of Raismes now wants to rehabilitate it. The building is composed of classrooms, a catering satellite and a gymnasium.

The renovation project is part of a municipal approach in order to then replicate it on the scale of the agglomeration.

The objective is to achieve E=0 over 20 years via the Energiesprong approach. The project began in December 2022 and was delivered in September 2023.

General Data	
Address	Ecole Anne Godeau
Year of renovation	2023
Housing owner	City of Raismes
General contractor	HDF Construction
Panel manufacturer	HDF Construction

Building information	
Year of construction	1967
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	3
Number of dwellings	-
Balconies	No
Total living area (m ²)	1,962 m ²
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	654 m ²
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure from the 70s
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Gas boiler centralized
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	223

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	No, move out for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	730
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure	Traditional ext insulation
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Biobased
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, technical local
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	4501377
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	747
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	22
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E = 0
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	20 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	

Roubaix

The first Energiesprong renovation project on a collective housing. Vilogia is applying the Energiesprong approach for the first time to collective housing. The residence targeted by the project is the Philippe Le Hardi residence. It is located in Roubaix. It consists of 32 housing units that were built in the 1950s. This project, which began in October 2021, is partly financed by the European fund Interreg North West Europe (NWE).

The Energiesprong approach and its E=0 renovation objectives, lower cost and speed, thanks to the use of prefabricated was selected. The objective of the project is to renovate energy-intensive housing into E=0 housing. Indeed, the aim is to enable them to produce as much energy as they consume for 25 years. In addition, the approach aims to improve the thermal and acoustic comfort of tenants as well as their living environment. Finally, these renovations will result in a significant reduction in energy bills for residents.

General Data	
Address	Rue d'Oran
Year of renovation	2022
Housing owner	Vilogia
General contractor	-
Panel manufacturer	BuildUp Offsite

Building information	
Year of construction	1950
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	4
Number of dwellings	32
Balconies	No
Total living area (m2)	1,450 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Individual gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	336

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	No, dwellings were empty when renovation occurred
Tenant engagement process	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	100%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Metal - Large panels - With glazing
Panel weight handling	Hanged to existing facades
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	No
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes - Collective ext modules
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	60
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E=0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	25 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Saint-Jean-de-Vedas

Saint-Jean de Védas is located in the Montpellier metropolitan area, in the South of France. The building of the Escholiers elementary school was renovated there according to the Energiesprong approach. It is a public school with 243 students. Following these renovations, the school changed its name and is now called the Georges Rascol school.

The project was carried out as part of a program to maintain, modernize and improve the comfort of the school heritage of the city of Saint-Jean-de-Védas.

On the one hand, these renovations result in E=0 over 20 years. This guarantees better living conditions for students. In addition, this zero energy level contributes to the challenges of France's National Low Carbon Strategy. On the other hand, all the work was carried out during the summer of 2022. Indeed, the project began in May 2022 and was inaugurated in November 2022. It was these requirements for results, both in terms of energy and speed on site, which were the decisive elements for the city in their choice to carry out this first Energiesprong school renovation project in France.

General Data	
Address	Les Escholiers
Year of renovation	2022
Housing owner	City of SJDV
General contractor	Sogea (Vinci)
Panel manufacturer	Sogea (Vinci)

Building information	
Year of construction	1970
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	-
Balconies	No
Total living area (m2)	1,500 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	
Roof surface (m2)	750 m ²

Type of structure	Classic concrete structure from the 70s
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	Gas boiler centralized
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	110

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation?	Yes
Volume increase?	No
Scaffoldings?	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation?	No, move out for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	150
% facade renovated offsite	75%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Metal - Large panels - With glazing
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Biobased
Photovoltaic panels	Yes
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel?	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	1,191,200
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	337
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	30
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E = 0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	20 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Vaulx-en-velin

The Noirettes and Grand Bois residences are located in Vaulx-en-Velin, in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region. Est Métropole Habitat has rehabilitated 988 homes there, spread across 9 buildings. These were built in the 1970s. This is the first project in France of such a scale inspired by the Energiesprong approach.

The renovation, with 42% prefabricated facade, made it possible to renovate almost 1,000 homes and to reduce the duration of the construction site to 19 months. Thanks to this technique, the buildings were able to be rehabilitated quickly and efficiently. In addition, this process of industrialized facade rehabilitation made it possible to thermally insulate the homes, optimize deadlines and minimize nuisances for tenants. Finally, bio-sourced materials from the circular economy were used.

General Data	
Address	Noirettes et Grand Bois (Mas du Taureau)
Year of renovation	2021
Housing owner	Est Metropole Habitat
General contractor	Vinci Construction
Panel manufacturer	Arbonis

Building information	
Year of construction	1972
Number of buildings	9
Number of floors (ground floor included)	9
Number of dwellings	988
Balconies	No
Total living area (m2)	66000
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Collective gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	182

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	42%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wood - Large panels - Without glazing
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to existing facades
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Wood only for structure
Photovoltaic panels	No
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	No need to change windows
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system	No
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	120
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	0%
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	No
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Wattrelos

Wattrelos is located in the European Metropolis of Lille. There are 160 social housing units there. These were targeted by an energy renovation project, because the district, dating from the 1960s, was then aging. This project concerns 400 inhabitants. Vilogia intended to transform this housing estate made up of energy-intensive houses into E=0 housing in record time. To do this, they applied the Energiesprong approach which consists of an “off-site” energy renovation. This is the first renovation project on this scale in France and Europe – outside the Netherlands!

The idea behind the project is on the one hand to transform these homes into buildings that meet the European objectives of 2050 and on the other hand to carry out the renovations, while respecting the inhabitants. It is also about providing a better quality of life for tenants by ensuring greater comfort. In addition, the project has contributed to the development of the region's economic activity thanks to the increased skills of local construction players in off-site activity. Finally, the speed of the works was a great asset. The project began in 2020 and was delivered in 2022.

General Data	
Address	Quartier de Beaulieu
Year of renovation	2021
Housing owner	Vilogia
General contractor	Rabot Dutilleul Construction
Panel manufacturer	BuildUp Offiste

Building information	
Year of construction	1960
Number of buildings	154
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	154
Balconies	No
Total living area (m2)	13,900 m ²
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Classic concrete structure

Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Individual gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	313

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, for small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for total duration
Tenant engagement process	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	50%
% roof renovated offsite	100%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Metal - Large panels - With glazing
Panel weight handling	New ground foundations
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Wood for facades
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes - Internal module
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	60
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	All : E=0
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	25 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Bochum, Katharinastrasse

The project concerns the serial and in-depth redevelopment of three residential buildings from the 1950s with 24 apartments. The use of prefabricated facade modules made it possible to reduce the activities on the construction site and therefore the disturbance for the residents. In particular, the facade insulation involved the use of prefabricated and pre-finished elements with a wooden structure while the roof was redone and the attic floor, which is occupied by some of the systems, was insulated.

The roof houses a photovoltaic system for the production of electricity which powers a water-water heat pump in combination with geothermal probes for heating and the production of domestic hot water. The new heat generator allows you to generate 4.5 kWh of heat for every 1 kWh of electricity: it is a system particularly suitable for existing buildings but requires a properly insulated casing. Thanks to the reduction in heating and maintenance costs, a return on investment is expected in 10 years.

General Data	
Address	Katharinastrass, Bochum
Year of renovation	2022
Housing owner	Vonovia SE
General contractor	Fischbach Gruppe GmbH
Panel manufacturer	Fischbach Gruppe GmbH

Building information	
Year of construction	1955
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	4
Number of dwellings	24
Balconies	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	1164
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	-
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	158

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	150
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	Yes
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber structure, 1 floor height, windows integrated
Panel weight handling	Hanged to existing facade
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, on the roof
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	2,5 million
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	20,13
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Bochum, Mörikestrasse

The intervention involved a residential building built in 1968 with 32 apartments. The Net Zero standard was achieved by installing 105 highly insulated pre-fabricated façade modules with a wooden structure and external finish and a new flat roof with photovoltaic modules.

The apartments received new units for heating, domestic hot water production and controlled mechanical ventilation, with the extraction of air from the bathroom and kitchen and the introduction of air at a controlled temperature by heat pumps. Furthermore, the apartments have been enlarged and made brighter with the transformation of the existing loggias and the installation of generous 8m² balconies. The common outdoor spaces were also redeveloped to resolve accessibility problems, as well as the stairwells and the doors were replaced with new aluminum elements with insulating glass. A halving of heating costs and a reduction in the costs of electricity supplied by the photovoltaic system are expected.

General Data	
Address	Mörikestrasse, Bochum
Year of renovation	2021
Housing owner	VBW Bauen and Wohnen GmbH
General contractor	B&O Group
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1968
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	4
Number of dwellings	32
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	2368
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	-

"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	142

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	-
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	180
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	Yes
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber structure, 1 floor height
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to existing facade
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel?	-
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	-
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	4,5 million
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	30
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Cologne

The project was born with the aim of quickly and cost-effectively redeveloping the four-storey condominium built in 1962, improving its energy performance from low efficiency to a Net Zero standard and guaranteeing continuity of living for the inhabitants during the entire construction period. In particular, the envelope was redeveloped using prefabricated facade panels with integrated windows and doors and prefabricated roofing elements.

At the plant level, the existing heat generator was replaced by a centralized heat pump with new terminals, a photovoltaic system was installed on the roof, a ventilation system with heat recovery was integrated into the facade and intelligent control systems were installed. Furthermore, the architectural quality of the building was improved thanks to the installation of a high-quality facade finish and new larger and more transparent balconies.

General Data	
Address	Schwalbacher Straße, Cologne
Year of renovation	2023
Housing owner	Wohnungsgenossenschaft am Vorgebirgspark eG
General contractor	Zeller Kölmel Architekten GmbH Korona Holz & Haus GmbH Energiebüro vom Stein GmbH
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1962
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	4
Number of dwellings	16
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	992
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	-

"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	201

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	-
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	390
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	Yes
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber structure insulated with pre-assembled windows
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, photovoltaic system on the roof for CO ₂ -neutral electricity generation
Solar thermal panels?	-
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Facade-integrated ventilation system with heat recovery
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Heat pump for central heating, including storage
Monitoring system?	Smart sensors and thermostat valves
Total renovation cost (€)	1,9 million
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-10
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	100%
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Mönchengladbach

The project is part of a complex of buildings re-developed by five partners, including Saint-Gobain, which applied the PreFormance solution in this project. The buildings, constructed in 1956, were selected for their geometric simplicity and potential for replicability.

The deep retrofit involved the use of prefabricated envelope elements, the replacement of the heat generation system with an air-water heat pump, storage systems for domestic hot water, ventilation systems and photovoltaic panels.

General Data	
Address	Mönchengladbach
Year of renovation	2023
Housing owner	LEG Immobilien SE
General contractor	Ecoworks GmbH
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1956
Number of buildings	5
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	20
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	1000
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	-
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	205

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	-
Volume increase	-
Scaffoldings	Yes
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Prefabricated facade elements including insulation, windows and doors
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, photovoltaic systems as roof-mounted
Solar thermal panels?	-
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Building services module integrated into the facade, which houses the heating and hot water pipes
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	-
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	50
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Catania

The case study consists of a multi-storey residential building in the city of Catania, owned by the Istituto Autonomo Case Popolari (IACP). The construction system is a reinforced concrete frame. The intervention involves the application of an integrated retrofit technology, a new building envelope made up of a combination of prefabricated wood-based panels that act as both thermal insulation and structural reinforcement. Specifically, the seismic performance is provided by cross-laminated timber (X-Lam or e-CLT) panels fixed to the building's reinforced concrete beams using innovative friction-based seismic dampers. The X-Lam panels are combined with timber frame panels (e-PANEL) for thermal insulation, to be installed on the building's windowed walls, together with new high-efficiency energy windows to replace the existing ones. Finally, the intervention includes the creation of a new mechanical system (e-THERM) for the production and distribution of hot water, which includes high-efficiency air-to-water heat pumps powered by on-site photovoltaic energy production, a central storage tank for thermal energy storage and decentralised storage tanks for distribution to individual residential units.

General Data	
Address	Via Acquicella Porto, Catania
Year of renovation	2024 - 2025
Housing owner	Istituto Autonomo Case Popolari (IACP)
General contractor	-
Panel manufacturer	E-Safe - Wedest

Building information	
Year of construction	1964
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	5
Number of dwellings	10
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	-
Facade surface (m ²)	1230
Roof surface (m ²)	-

Type of structure	Reinforced concrete frame and walls made of lightweight concrete blocks
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Gas boilers
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	50 %
% roof renovated offsite	N/A
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber XLAM structure, 18 cm thick, 60 to 100 km/m ²
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Localized anchoring on friction-based seismic damper
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel?	No, installed separately
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	300
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	Yes
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Corte Franca, Brescia

The first Energiesprong intervention in Southern Europe took place in the municipality of Corte Franca (BS). For the first time in Italy, a building was retrofitted to NZEB standards using offsite technologies, with prefabricated panels installed in less than a week and without disturbing the occupants. The removal of gas, on-site energy production and improved insulation will reduce cumulative emissions by over 75% by 2050 compared to the pre-intervention state. The NZEB energy efficiency and seismic retrofit intervention was carried out through new facades and roofs made of prefabricated wood panels, with a new external perimeter foundation, while the deteriorated balconies were demolished and rebuilt off-site.

The chosen energy system solution is fully electric, with a heat pump, a photovoltaic system with storage and a solar thermal system. The new systems are located in the attic, and heat and hot water are distributed through vertical shafts in the thickness of the new facades, accessible from the outside for maintenance. The project integrates seismic safety and energy performance with off-site solutions in record time. The 18 prefabricated panels covering the building's facades were installed at a rate of one per hour, with the entire installation taking less than a week to complete.

General Data	
Address	Via Roma 103 Colombaro di Corte Franca
Year of renovation	2021
Housing owner	Private
General contractor	Woodbeton
Panel manufacturer	Woodbeton

Building information	
Year of construction	1973
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	5
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	551
Facade surface (m ²)	378

Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	Concrete frame
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	Autonomous gas heat generator
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	213

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes
Tenant engagement process?	No
Total onsite works duration (days)	160
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	Yes
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	140
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber structure, vertical orientation
Panel weight handling (ex. handed to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Supported by new perimeter curb and facade anchoring
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes
Solar thermal panels?	Yes
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	New vertical distribution in facade thickness accessible from exterior
Windows integrated in the panel?	No
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, under the roof
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	475
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	41
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	64
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	Yes
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Greve in Chianti, Florence

The retrofit of the public social housing building in Greve in Chianti was carried out within the framework of the European H2020 INFINITE project. The existing building complex consists of two mirror-image twin buildings of two storeys and a ground-floor pilotis entrance level. Each of the two buildings, part of the public residential heritage managed by Casa Spa, comprises four apartments of approximately 80 square metres each. The intervention was carried out on one of the two twin buildings, allowing for a future comparison of the economic and energy impacts of a retrofit based on traditional methods versus prefabrication and industrialization of processes.

The project involved the demolition of the existing roof and the deteriorated balconies. The roof was replaced with 250 m² of offsite modular covering. The balconies, also prefabricated, were installed together with the façades directly on site. To allow for these operations, new foundations were provided for the pillars supporting the balconies. All four elevations were clad with 400 m² of multifunctional prefabricated panels having a timber-frame structure, manufactured by Fanti, and hosting the various technologies developed by the INFINITE project: air ducts, smart windows, integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and solar thermal (BIST). The off-site elements have been produced in 3 months in the factory and installed in 4 days onsite, while the finishing (including BIPV) took 3 weeks. For mechanical ventilation, the reconstruction of the balconies allowed for an inclusion of the ventilation units within the parapet, to make maintenance fully accessible. In addition, two centralized heat pumps have been installed for heating/ cooling and hot water. A BMS (Building Management System) managed by Casa SpA monitors the operation of the building's technical systems and allows the user to identify, via an app, the potential economic impact on their energy bills. The building after the renovation reached a nZEB target: full-electric systems for a decrease in energy consumptions and GHG emission of around 90%.

General Data	
Address	Via di Colognole, Greve in Chianti
Year of renovation	2024 - 2025
Housing owner	Municipality, managed by Casa Spa
General contractor	-
Panel manufacturer	Fanti Legnami

Building information	
Year of construction	1979
Number of buildings	2
Number of floors (ground floor included)	3
Number of dwellings	8
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	650 m ²
Facade surface (m ²)	400 m ²
Roof surface (m ²)	250m ²
Type of structure	Concrete frame
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Autonomous heating system and domestic hot water produced with individual gas boilers
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	270
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	100%
New balconies?	Yes
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	100 m ² / day
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wooden facade panels
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to the existing facade. New foundations for balconies
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Yes, wood-based panels

Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, BIPV (building integrated photovoltaic), 48% self-consumption target
Solar thermal panels?	Yes, BIST (building integrated solar thermal) for DHW (domestic hot water)
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Pipes for ventilation integrated in the facade
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, 2 heat pumps in the technical room with external unit
Monitoring system?	Pre monitoring data collection has begun
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

IN-DEPTH FOCUS - GREVE IN CHIANTI

Technical system integration

The Greve in Chianti project enabled the integration and testing of advanced technologies across multiple building elements: facades, roofs, windows and balconies.

Smart windows & smart glazing

Windows, with frames integrated offsite into the façade modules, include louvre shading systems within the double-glazed unit (IGU), installed in all rooms, also on north-facing windows for privacy purposes. The system can be operated manually or via the Next Sense sensor installed on the external face of the glazing, which regulates the louvre position through a sensor responding to incident solar radiation.

Building integrated photovoltaic system (BIPV)

BIPV was installed on both the roof and the east and west façades in an oxidised red colour that echoes the passive cladding of the rest of the building, so to achieve a unified aesthetic result.

For the BIPV (Building-Integrated Photovoltaics), the Suncol system by SUNAGE was integrated on the east and south roof pitches for a total of 80 m², while on the east and west façades 55 m² of panels were installed in oxidised red colour, that echoes the passive cladding of the rest of the building for a uniform aesthetic result. The roof modules in basalt grey, with an average size of 125×82 cm, deliver an efficiency of approximately 130 Wp/m² (13%), while the façade modules in oxidised red have a base dimension of 110×73 cm with an efficiency of approximately 135 Wp/m² (13.5%).

Solar-thermal generation system (BIST)

The integration of the BIST technology involved the installation of 80 m² on the south façade, characterised by a finish in oxidised red similar to the passive cladding and the BIPV panels. The original design included a hydraulic system to support the heat pump for heating and domestic hot water (DHW) production, which was subsequently excluded due to technical difficulties in the operation of the technology. A key upgrade of the BIST system within the INFINITE project was the development of a plug & play connection system for the panels produced by SERNEO and the timber façade modules. The related assembly occurred offsite at the FANTI manufacturing plant.

Energy and fresh air distribution system

Four VORTICE ventilation units for heating, cooling, and fresh air renewal, each with a flow rate of approximately 250 m³/h, were integrated into the new prefabricated balconies — two per apartment (with a floor area of 90 m²) — avoiding any invasive works on the existing masonry walls. This solution allows full access to the units for ordinary and extraordinary maintenance, minimising disruption to residents. The distribution plenums are also accessible from the balcony for cleaning of the air ducts, while the supply, extract, and recirculation ducts have been fully embedded within the prefabricated façades and connected to the internal grilles of each room. The routing of the ducts was achieved through openings in the timber frame uprights, with insulation ensured by the rock wool inserted in the panels.

Passeggiata dei Castani, Bolzano

The project features two social housing buildings with 72 residential units, situated at Via Passeggiata dei Castani 33 in Bolzano, Italy. The renovation action development aimed to provide affordable housing while meeting strict sustainability and energy efficiency requirements. The construction site was strategically organized to enhance installation and finishing workflows, cutting production and construction time by 60%, particularly through rapid façade installation reaching 225 m² daily.

A distinctive feature of the project is its innovative prefabricated timber façades. These multifunctional elements combine architectural appeal with practical benefits, incorporating premium windows and external shading systems (movable external venetian blinds) that maximize energy efficiency and resident comfort. Given that this was the first Italian experience of this kind, the design team and customer decided to pass through a mockup and preliminary testing phase (performed by Eurac Research) to check the feasibility and the expected performances of such complex prefabricated façade system.

The engineering design included a centralized heating system delivering both domestic hot water and space heating. The renovation also included a dual efficiency heat pump coupled to 16 geothermal probes, each extending 150 meters underground. This system delivers 73% of the required space heating, minimizing fossil fuel usage. Building first block has a roof-mounted photovoltaic system, sized to power the central heating system's heat pumps and supporting common area energy needs for one building. Building second block's rooftop featured advanced solar thermal collectors, designed to supply 59% of the total hot water needs.

Both buildings employ decentralized mechanical ventilation systems to maintain optimal indoor air quality while reducing heat loss. Additionally, twenty-seven units are equipped with monitoring systems tracking window usage and energy consumption

patterns. This monitoring enables detailed analysis of resident behavior, supporting targeted improvements in energy efficiency and user engagement.

General Data	
Address	Via Passeggiata dei Castani 33, Bolzano (BZ)
Year of renovation	2017 - 2019
Housing owner	Municipality Bolzano
General contractor	Carron Bau Srl
Panel manufacturer	Aster Holzbau, San Genesio
Design	Smaprogetti (TO)*
Building information	
Year of construction	1989
Number of buildings	2
Number of floors (ground floor included)	6
Number of dwellings	72
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	7.364 mq
Facade surface (m ²)	6.019 mq
Roof surface (m ²)	1.866 mq
Type of structure	Concrete frame
Energy generation pre-renovation	Autonomous heating system and domestic hot water produced with individual gas boilers
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	yes (97 mq)
Scaffoldings	yes
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration	540 days
% facade renovated offsite	64%
% roof renovated offsite	none
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time	225 mq/day
Panel structure	Wooden façade panels (2,9x6 m) with glasswool, wood fiber HD and alluminium as external cladding

Panel weight handling	hanged on concrete frame
Circular/ biobased materials?	Wood as load bearing structure
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes on the roof for 52 KWp (not integrated)
Solar thermal panels?	Yes on the roof (not integrated)
Systems integrated in the panel?	Yes, shading system (venetian blinds), ventilation pipes
Windows integrated in the panel?	No
Heat pump?	Yes, in the technical room
Monitoring system?	Pre monitoring data collection has begun
Total renovation cost (€)	5.394.130 €
Facade cost, supply and installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation	22,5 kWh/mq*y (12 kW/mq*y envelope efficiency)
% consumption covered by renewables	81% PV, 59% ST
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	2 years
Lessons learnt	Construction times reduced by 60%, quality control off site ed on site

Pieve Emanuele

The project involves the energy and seismic renovation of 5 buildings in the former INCIS residential area in Pieve Emanuele. The current condition of the buildings highlighted poor maintenance, with specific issues with the stability of the façade cladding and insulation. The selected solution dry system was applied to about half of the total surface area of the façades; the energy and seismic renovation intervention was carried out using prefabricated insulating panels (ISOPAN ADDVision) with a vertical metal finish and a metal substructure anchored at the floor levels, ensuring the anti-tipping stability of the perimeter walls. The other half adopted traditional EPS insulation. The junction between the two different façade materials was resolved with the application of pre-painted aluminum flashing. Similarly, the new flashing elements replaced items such as gutters, downspouts, and window reveals.

The use of pantograph platforms instead of traditional scaffolding maintained the visual accessibility of the buildings and the comfort inside the apartments.

General Data	
Address	Via Donizetti, via Mascagni, via Zandonai, via Zandonai, Pieve Emanuele, Milano
Year of renovation	2024
Housing owner	Private
General contractor	PT System
Panel manufacturer	Isopan

Building information	
Year of construction	1969-1770
Number of buildings	5 (4 long and 1 short)
Number of floors (ground floor included)	5
Number of dwellings	238 (52 for the long, 30 the short)
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m ²)	5 580
Facade surface (m ²)	12 000
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	Reinforced concrete frame with beams and columns

Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	50%
% roof renovated offsite	N/A
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	130
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Steel frame and sandwich panel with polyisocyanurate insulation, vertical 350x100 cm
Panel weight handling (ex. changed to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Steel wall bracket
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	No
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No systems integrated into the panels
Windows integrated in the panel?	No
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system?	No
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	160 €/m ² for supply + installation
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	Yes, anti-tipping stability of the perimeter walls
Performance guarantee duration	1 year
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Povo, Trento

The intervention is located in Povo, Trento, and was carried out as part of the European ARV project, funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 program, in which Fanti participates as a third party of Habitech-Trentino Technological District. In the context of the general renovation of the building, consisting of 9 residential units, the project includes the installation of an insulating cladding of a shared photovoltaic system, and the replacement of windows and individual boilers. On two façades, the Renew-Wall modular system, with a wooden-based structure, was installed for the energy and architectural renovation of existing buildings. The Renew-Wall system focuses on architectural aspects of absolute distinction also due to an ETA, patents for the connections and seals to ensure durability, and the ability to finish the panel externally in the factory with efficient and cost-effective solutions. The finish used in Povo is a plaster finish, the same as the one used on the rest of the building, but completed offsite.

General Data	
Address	Povo, Trento
Year of renovation	2023
Housing owner	Private
General contractor	Fanti Group
Panel manufacturer	Fanti Group

Building information	
Year of construction	1952
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	3
Number of dwellings	9
Balconies?	Yes, on the side not interested by the prefabricated elements
Total living area (m2)	-
Facade surface (m2)	800
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Load-bearing stone masonry
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Autonomous gas boilers
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	16 %
% roof renovated offsite	N/A
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time (m2/day)	50 to 80
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber structure and insulation between OSB and DWD panels, insulation against existing, ventilated facade with plaster finishing. Max dim 350x800 cm.
Panel weight handling (exchanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Linear or localized anchoring
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Not in this case but possible
Windows integrated in the panel?	No
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system?	No
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	250 to 300
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Progetto definitivo in esecuzione (Credits: Fanti Group e Gabriele Zini)

Russoli, Milan

The project for the residential complex consisting of four towers on Via Russoli, Milan, is developed on parallel levels: environment, city, people, and sustainability.

From an environmental perspective, the energy refurbishment of the complex involved the use of pre-fabricated façades made from bio-based materials, with the aim of achieving a real and conscious optimization of resources and a rational use of energy from the city's district heating network. The vertical envelope was thermally insulated by replacing windows and shutters. Additionally, from the plant perspective, a photovoltaic system with storage was installed, the heating plant was renovated, and systems for temperature regulation and metering were added. The surrounding area was also revitalized through deeply regenerative actions on the common spaces. Special attention was given to the tenants, including the creation of garden spaces and green areas on the previously underutilized flat roofs, with the ultimate goal of fostering social interaction. The interventions allowed the complex to achieve an energy class of A4.

General Data	
Address	Via Russoli, Milano
Year of renovation	2022 - 2023
Housing owner	Aler (Lombard Agency for Residential Buildings)
General contractor	A2a calore e servizi
Panel manufacturer	Woodbeton, design Tiziana Monterisi Architetto

Building information	
Year of construction	1978
Number of buildings	4
Number of floors (ground floor included)	9
Number of dwellings	187
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m2)	10900
Facade surface (m2)	12000
Roof surface (m2)	2900
Type of structure	-

Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Partially, for corner balconies
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time (m2/day)	140
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Timber structure, horizontal direction, 1 floor height
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to the existing facade
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Bio-based RiceHouse insulation materials made from rice waste
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel?	No
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	-
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	Yes
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Picture credits: Beatrice Avrenella

Drive 0, Case 6

Three representative single family buildings with poor existing energy efficiency in different locations were identified and deeply renovated and implementing circular principles, focusing around material circularity using recyclable mineral wool thermal, acoustic and fire safe insulation with innovative bio-based binder for whole building envelope, newly tested ventilated façade system, 2D prefabricated façade insulated panels, new thermally efficient windows, efficient and renewable-energy powered installations and more. All demo buildings constitute of masonry walls and reinforced concrete slabs with wooden rafter pitched roofs with owners possessing certain levels of DIY construction skills, so homeowner's centric approach to renovation and circularity was also an important study parameter.

General Data	
Address	Kandrše del, Slovenia
Year of renovation	2022
Housing owner	private person
General contractor	none, individual
Panel manufacturer	Rihter

Building information	
Year of construction	1988
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	3
Number of dwellings	1 https://ipi.eprostor.gov.si/jv/?e id=100200000224437927%26100300000296460202
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m2)	~160
Facade surface (m2)	?
Roof surface (m2)	55 (area under building)
Type of structure	Reinforced concrete
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Grid electricity Wood stoves
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	109 https://www.drive0.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Drive-0_-D6.5.pdf

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	Yes
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation?	No, dwellings were empty when renovation occurred
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	~200
% facade renovated offsite	~10
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies?	Yes, demolished and hanged to new facade
Facade installation time (m2/day)	~10
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wood, minor part as test
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to existing, few 100 kg
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Wood, recycled mineral wool
Photovoltaic panels?	No
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel?	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, in the boiler room
Monitoring system?	No
Total renovation cost (€)	160k
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	Not available
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	35 according to building physics
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	Not available jet
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	Not available jet
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	Not known
Lessons learnt (optional)	Very satisfied customer

Ravne na Koroškem

Context

The INFINITE Slovenian demonstration case is in Ravne na Koroškem, a medium-size town in northern Slovenia characterised by limited land availability due to its valley geography. The demo building is a multi-storey, mixed-use residential block built between the 1970s and 1980s, with residential units above non-residential ground-floor spaces. Despite being connected to district heating, the building showed poor energy performance, mainly due to an inefficient envelope and outdated systems.

The social dimension of the building is equally significant: it originally housed workers from nearby industrial facilities and later became part of the municipality's temporary housing system for socially vulnerable groups. This function contributed to a negative social perception: addressing both technical underperformance and social stigma was therefore a key ambition of the renovation.

Renovation strategy and densification

The Slovenian demo adopted a dual strategy, combining an industrialised deep renovation of the existing building with densification through the addition of a new prefabricated floor. This approach made it possible to improve the performance and living conditions of existing dwellings while responding to housing demand without consuming additional land.

Structural assessments confirmed that the building could support additional loads, while a close dialogue with the municipality ensured compliance with planning regulations for increased height and volume. Densification also played a crucial role from a business perspective. The creation of six new housing units on the added floor generated revenue that contributed to financing the deep renovation of the existing building.

The renovation followed an iterative design process, supported by a detailed digital survey based on laser scanning and a continuously updated building information model. The implementation adopted a mixed approach:

conventional external insulation systems were installed on site where prefabricated solutions were not applied

the core industrialised deep renovation elements and the new top floor were prefabricated off site, integrating insulation, structure and selected building services and were assembled on site with reduced disruption.

Building-integrated photovoltaics was completed on site.

Achieved impact and results

The renovation aimed to achieve near-zero energy building performance, combining envelope upgrading, renewable energy integration and improved building services.

Resident surveys and monitoring data showed substantial improvements in thermal comfort and indoor air quality after the intervention. Winter-to-winter comparisons confirmed that these improvements were not driven by seasonal effects alone. Reports of uncomfortable temperatures and poor air quality were drastically reduced, while overall satisfaction increased significantly.

One of the most relevant outcomes of this building lies in its social and urban impact: the renovation improved the image and functionality of the building without displacing existing residents. The intervention stabilised the social mix while improving housing quality and living conditions for both existing and new occupants.

General Data	
Address	Ob suhi, Ravne na koroškem, Slovenia
Year of renovation	2024
Housing owner	STAN
General contractor	Exit
Panel manufacturer	Lesoteka for renovation, Žiher for new floor

Building information	
Year of construction	1982
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	5
Number of dwellings	71
Balconies	Yes
Total living area (m2)	2.654 (gross) 2527 conditioned
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	543 (area under building)
Type of structure	Reinforced concrete
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	"Grid electricity District heating system District heating and centralized electrical heating tank"
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	166 (primary energy), heating 51, needed for operation 95 according to EPC

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	Yes
Scaffoldings	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process?	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	Not available yet, still in proces
% facade renovated offsite	~1/4
% roof renovated offsite	100%
New balconies?	No, traditional renovation of existing balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	~70
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wood, ~6x2

Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to existing, few 100 kg
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Wood, mineral wool
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Yes, ventilation, cables and pipes
Windows integrated in the panel?	No need to change windows
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	yes, next to the building
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	Not available yet
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	Not available yet
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	Not available yet
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	Not available yet
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	Not available yet
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	Not available yet
Lessons learnt (optional)	Not available yet

Aligra

The latest modification of the Catalan Urban Planning Law (2022) allows the volumetric expansion of residential properties in exchange for implementing substantial improvements in their habitability, accessibility and water and energy efficiency. They are structures that add a new façade to buildings, allowing them to gain space through balconies, new rooms or community areas while improving their insulation and comfort. They also include installing solar panels, green roofs and rainwater harvesting systems on rooftops. December 2022 – March 2024: Manufacture and installation of the prototypes. April 2024- May 2025: Monitoring of the prototypes (to assess their impact on health and comfort, urban resilience, energy efficiency, circular economy and biodiversity).

Aligra is an integrated system of prefabricated timber modules designed for the renovation and expansion of residential buildings. The system is based on a wide range of prefabricated modules that adapt to all kinds of architectural pre-existences, weather contexts and regulatory frameworks. These are two-dimensional modules composed of different wooden elements. Their dimensions and lightness facilitate handling, storage, transportation and installation. They are assembled by means of reversible and accessible joints that facilitate assembly, repair, reuse and recycling. Furthermore, the modules are combined with each other in order to configure five three-dimensional kits that respond to different recurring needs: the insulation of facades, the addition of galleries or terraces, the creation of photovoltaic canopies, the use of cisterns to accumulate rainwater and the deployment of smart sensors to monitor the performance of the building. Over the course of a year, its sensors will collect indicators to test the water and energy efficiency of this open source solution, which is completely free of proprietary patents.

General Data	
Address	Campus Diagonal-Besòs. Avinguda d'Eduard Maristany, 16 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs. Barcelona
Year of renovation	23/02/2024
Housing owner	BIT Habitat foundation. Barcelona City Council
General contractor	Straddle3, Societat Orgànica, Aiguasol, Tallfusta and Tejido
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	N/A
Number of buildings	N/A
Number of floors (ground floor included)	N/A
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	N/A
Total living area (m2)	N/A
Facade surface (m2)	N/A
Roof surface (m2)	N/A
Type of structure	N/A
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	N/A

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	N/A
Volume increase	Yes
Type of structure	Aligra has a wide range of cladding panels that respond to the construction system of the ventilated façade.
Scaffoldings	
Inhabited during renovation?	N/A. It is a prototype
Tenant engagement process?	N/A
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	100 %
% roof renovated offsite	100 %
New balconies?	-
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-

Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Aligra has a wide range of cladding panels that respond to the construction system of the ventilated façade. They are able to cover façades and party walls of existing buildings and also adapt to the other kits in the system. Based on a structural frame made of light wooden framework, each module offers the possibility of adding or replacing certain layers to improve its performance. The finishes off
Panel weight handling (ex. handed to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	It can be both options, handed to the existing facade or to the new structural frame (self-supported) made of microlaminated wood (LVL) that are attached to the facades of existing buildings.
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Structural frames made of microlaminated wood (LVL). Rainwater cistern is made from reused high-density polyethylene (HDPE) fruit boxes.
Photovoltaic panels?	They can be both types, installed on roof in a traditional way and integrated in the facade.
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Rainwater cisterns collect and accumulate rainwater on the roofs of pre-existing buildings, after checking their capacity to handle the excess weight, or on the enlarged parts. Bioclimatic ventilation panel with an active system integrated in the panel.
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	187,500.00
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	No
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

InnoFAB

The latest modification of the Catalan Urban Planning Law (2022) allows the volumetric expansion of residential properties in exchange for implementing substantial improvements in their habitability, accessibility and water and energy efficiency. They are structures that add a new façade to buildings, allowing them to gain space through balconies, new rooms or community areas while improving their insulation and comfort. They also include installing solar panels, green roofs and rainwater harvesting systems on rooftops. December 2022 – March 2024: Manufacture and installation of the prototypes. April 2024- May 2025: Monitoring of the prototypes (to assess their impact on health and comfort, urban resilience, energy efficiency, circular economy and biodiversity).

InnoFAB project proposes a metal structure, hung or supported, with a series of components that provide the home with a larger exterior and interior surface, as well as optimal bioclimatic conditions and environmentally friendly finishes. The system allows the concept to be replicable and adaptable to a wide variety of situations and needs. It consists of the following main layers:

1. light metallic structure
2. Light corrugated sheet metal casing
3. 100% recyclable technological wood flooring with 70% local wood content and no toxicity
4. Solar protection
5. photovoltaic planter
6. Light roof with integration of renewable energy production
7. vegetation integration

All these layers are independent, they can be installed at any time, they can be dismantled and re-assembled in another building. This independence is achieved through the following system features:

- Modularity of 2.5m in plan
- Purely mechanical connections throughout the system
- Independent location of each system on the structure

Green roofs with rainwater storage and photovoltaic planters that combine vegetation and electricity generation. Lamps with the possibility of dimming and that can be turned on or off from the monitoring application.

General Data

Address	Campus Diagonal-Besòs. Avinguda d'Eduard Maristany, 16 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs. Barcelona
Year of renovation	23/02/2024
Housing owner	BIT Habitat foundation. Barcelona City Council
General contractor	Pich Aguilera Arquitectes, Pich Architects y Pich Innovation, Metalperfil Ros, Vertical Urban Biotechnology
Panel manufacturer	Garcia Faura

Building information

Year of construction	N/A
Number of buildings	N/A
Number of floors (ground floor included)	N/A
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	N/A
Total living area (m2)	N/A
Facade surface (m2)	N/A
Roof surface (m2)	N/A
Type of structure	N/A
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	N/A

Retrofit Information

Internal renovation	N/A
Volume increase	Yes
Type of structure	It is a metal structure, hung or supported, with a series of components that provide the home with a larger exterior and interior surface, as well as optimal bioclimatic conditions and environmentally friendly finishes.
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation?	N/A. It is a prototype
Tenant engagement process?	N/A

Total onsite works duration (days)	Assembly: 1 day. Finishing: 1 month, but it wasn't continuous work; each tradesperson came when it suited them. In total, the full days dedicated to the finishing work can be considered as 7.
% facade renovated offsite	100 %
% roof renovated offsite	100 %
New balconies?	Yes. There are 3 possibilities: hanged to existing facade at each floor; hanged to the existing building; and discharged to the ground.
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Industrialized, lightweight, multi-layer closure and finishing systems, with materials that, 80%, come from recycled products or that can be reused (Light corrugated sheet metal casing).
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Mechanical connections throughout the system
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	The windows are made of recycled aluminum and with low energy consumption glass and solar protection systems.
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Solar protection with automated blinds, connected to the Smart Building Kit, which controls the desired lighting level.
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	138,153.38
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	N/A
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	60% improvement in the thermal transmittance of the existing facades ($U = 0.30 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$) and 35% for the roof ($U = 0.29 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$)
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	Not calculated yet
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	Not calculated yet
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Photovoltaic planter

The planter is designed as an industrialized, modular product, with the aim to decrease terrace or a balcony of the user. It introduces vegetation to the façade, by giving a base to climbing plants that can efficiently cover the façade area. The planter provides an inclination to the photovoltaic panel closer to the optimal one, compared to vertical placement.

Integration of local renewable energy production for individual users. Introduction of vegetation to the façade or urban landscape both to improve the energy efficiency of buildings and the urban environment in terms of heat island and aesthetics.

General Data	
Address	-
Year of renovation	-
Housing owner	-
General contractor	-
Panel manufacturer	-
Useful links	-

Building information	
Year of construction	N/A
Number of buildings	N/A
Number of floors (ground floor included)	N/A
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	N/A
Total living area (m2)	N/A
Facade surface (m2)	N/A
Roof surface (m2)	N/A
Type of structure	N/A
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	N/A

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	N/A
Volume increase	No
Type of structures	Stainless steel

Scaffoldings	-
Inhabited during renovation?	-
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	-
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	-
Panel weight handling (ex. changed to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	-
Solar thermal panels?	-
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel?	-
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	-
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-

Lessons learnt (optional)

The complex urban development regulations and laws, the decision-making process between multiple property owners, difficult accessibility of the boundary walls, which in combination with the high maintenance needs of photovoltaic and green facades caused high installation and maintenance costs, and the lower energy production of the photovoltaic panels on the façade compared to roof and related business models, in overall led to the idea of developing the photovoltaic planter as a product instead of an integrated facade module.

Photovoltaic planter at Eco Hub

The planter is designed as an industrialized, modular product, with the aim to decrease terrace or a balcony of the user. It introduces vegetation to the façade, by giving a base to climbing plants that can efficiently cover the façade area. The planter provides an inclination to the photovoltaic panel closer to the optimal one, compared to vertical placement.

The photovoltaic planters were installed to the south wall of the building. Renovation of a hall into office and meeting space.

General Data	
Address	Barcelona
Year of renovation	-
Housing owner	ECO HUB
General contractor	Vertical
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	N/A
Number of buildings	N/A
Number of floors (ground floor included)	N/A
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	N/A
Total living area (m2)	N/A
Facade surface (m2)	N/A
Roof surface (m2)	N/A
Type of structure	N/A
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	N/A

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	N/A
Volume increase	No
Type of structure	Based on steel frame
Scaffoldings	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation?	N/A
Tenant engagement process?	N/A
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies-
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	-
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to the existing facade. Mechanical connections only.
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/facade
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	"Smart irrigation and management system with sensors"
Windows integrated in the panel?	N/A
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	N/A
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Photovoltaic planter at Gonsi

The planter is designed as an industrialized, modular product, with the aim to decrease terrace or a balcony of the user. It introduces vegetation to the façade, by giving a base to climbing plants that can efficiently cover the façade area. The planter provides an inclination to the photovoltaic panel closer to the optimal one, compared to vertical placement. The photovoltaic planters are installed on the roof of an office building, and demonstrates the capacity of the planter to be used instead of a railing as well.

General Data	
Address	Barcelona
Year of renovation	-
Housing owner	GONSI
General contractor	Vertical
Panel manufacturer	-
Building information	
Year of construction	N/A
Number of buildings	N/A
Number of floors (ground floor included)	N/A
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	N/A
Total living area (m2)	N/A
Facade surface (m2)	N/A
Roof surface (m2)	N/A
Type of structure	N/A
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	N/A

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	N/A
Volume increase	No
Type of structure	The system was especially designed to resolve the structural integrity of the installation without the need to penetrate the waterproofing layer of the roof.
Scaffoldings	-
Inhabited during renovation?	N/A
Tenant engagement process?	N/A
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	-
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Railing
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/facade
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	"Smart irrigation and management system with sensors"
Windows integrated in the panel?	N/A
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	N/A
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Plug-n-Harvest

Plug-n-play passive and active multimodal energy harvesting systems, circular economy by design, with high replicability for self-sufficient districts and near-zero buildings. The main strategic goal of the PLUG-N-HARVEST proposal is to design, develop, demonstrate and exploit a new modular, plug-n-play concept for ADBE- Adaptable/Dynamic Building Envelopes, deployable to both residential and non-residential existing buildings. The system should be able to provide the maximum possible energy use reduction and the maximum possible energy harvesting from RES (Renewable Energy Sources), both at the single-building and the district scale, while requiring medium-to-low installation costs and almost-zero operational costs.

System innovation

Considering the façade system as such, there are multiple advantages partly shared with other industrialized systems, but also unique features.

- The final developed prefabricated modular solution using an innovative profile- ADBE, manufactured by García Faura
- Includes window profiles from the same provider
- The solar shading length and position is adjustable
- The PV panels are well ventilated (min 10 cm ir gap + ventilation openings)
- The cladding is based on aluminium sheet and can have the same or different aspect as the profiles
- Ventilation of the PV panels- special ventilation profiles were added below and above the PV panels, in order to ensure the air flow behind these panels, while protecting the façade from rainwater. The ventilation helps to decrease the overheating of the PV panels and so to improve their efficiency.

General Data	
Address	"Sant Quirze del Vallès Ronda d'Arraona 29"
Year of renovation	2022
Housing owner	INCASÒL but managed by AHC.
General contractor	Picharchitects/Pich-Aguilera y Pich Innovation
Panel manufacturer	Garcia Faura

Building information	
Year of construction	2003
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	4
Number of dwellings	6
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	264,6 m2 (44,10 m2 each dwelling)
Facade surface (m2)	130,80 m2 (101 m2 renovated)
Roof surface (m2)	18,6 m2
Type of structure	The structure of the building has bidirectional concrete slabs (0,30 m thickness), reinforced steel bars, and pillars of 0,36 x 0,40 m. No pathologies in the structure have been detected.
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	There are electric radiators for heating and part of the domestic hot water demand is covered by means of solar thermal panels located in the rooftop of the building. There is no cooling system or capacity in the building. Electricity is the only source of energy.
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	257,5 kWh/m2 año (Primary non-renewable energy consumption)

Retrofit information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Type of structure	The structure of the panels is a framework formed by aluminium profiles with a section of 228 mm, composed of two separate pieces of aluminium to guarantee the breaking of the thermal bridge. The profile has three levels of waterproofing in its section. All the profiles are anodized matt silver, 15 microns. Regarding the openings, the panels will incorporate new windows, with double glazing and an aluminium frame with thermal break. The profile is 75 mm thick and complies with the thermal requirements of the Spanish Technical Code. A silver anodized aluminium railing is placed in front of the balcony at a height of 1100 mm for safety reasons and compliance with the SUA. The interior space of the panels, with a thickness of 10 cm, is filled with 100 mm mineral wool thermal insulation (described below), encapsulated by two 1,5 mm thick aluminium sheets. The outer faces of the panels are formed by aluminium sheets with a thickness of 3 mm (the full opaque parts). All sheets have been fixed using stainless screws according to DIN 7981.

Scaffoldings	None
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes
Tenant engagement process?	No
Total onsite works duration (days)	67 days The entire process of implementation can be broken down into 6 clearly differentiated steps: 1- Dismantling of the existing façade. 2- Preparation works for the implementation 3- Installation of the new ADBE façade panels 4- Dismantling of the existing windows from the interior 5- Finishing works: window frame, crowning and lateral of the façade, etc. 6- Placement of the PV modules."
% facade renovated offsite	Panels 100%
% roof renovated offsite	No
New balconies?	No
Facade installation time (m2/day)	Modules were installed in 54 days. 2 m2 per day.
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Aluminium panels that include an internal thermal insulation layer to reduce heat loss and exterior photovoltaic panels of amorphous silicon to generate electricity (in our case, with a photovoltaic installed capacity of 6.22 kWp). Thermal insulation and photovoltaic panels will only be installed on the opaque elements. The energy generated will be equally distributed to all homes in the property. The system will have plug-n-play features reducing the length of installation work.
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	L-profiles anchored to existing slabs and ceramic walls where modules are installed.
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Within the possibilities, the products with environmental features and available information were selected for the project, such as aluminium with the highest certified recycled content.
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Systems (ex. pipes/ cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel?	No
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	"HVAC: installation of individual electric heat pumps using aerothermal technology in every dwelling."

Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	178.778 € + IVA
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	same as total renovation
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	The new industrialized south facade with the ADBE system has a thermal transmittance of Opaque modules U=0.27 W/m2K and Windows U=1.18 W/m2K.
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	N/A
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Plural

The building is composed of two residential blocks, and a commercial space (not included in the pilot case). All of them are placed in a "U" form with a common courtyard in the middle. PLURAL solutions will be implemented in one block (18 dwellings). The Denvelops Comfort Wall is an off-site prefabricated ventilated façade system composed of vertical stainless-steel guidelines and connectors that allow to attach and bear loads of the cladding. The cladding system is made of 1 mm thick painted aluminium cladding tiles with resistant powder coating. PV panels are integrated into the façade, locally replacing the final cladding. The thermal insulation is made of mineral wool and is protected by a weathering layer. Both are attached to the system's vertical guidelines in order to achieve the required thermal and water-tightness performance. The mineral wool is covered by a glass-fibre layer that can protect against mechanical damage. Thermal resistance equal to $2.90(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})/\text{W}$ is achieved with a 100 mm thick Denvelops Comfort Wall façade, considered the optimum passive measure.

The Denvelops Comfort Wall contains an innovative HVAC system called Air Handling Unit (AHU) developed by Czech Technical University and located in a vertical position. The AHU incorporates two stages of heat recovery: the first is a passive heat exchanger (plate), and the second is an active heat exchanger with thermoelectric modules that provides supply air temperature control. The unit is connected to the interior space via supply and extract channels. The electric power for the thermoelectric modules is derived from the PVs or the grid.

General Data	
Address	Terrassa
Year of renovation	-
Housing owner	-
General contractor	-
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	-

Number of buildings	-
Number of floors (ground floor included)	-
Number of dwellings	-
Balconies?	-
Total living area (m2)	-
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	-
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	-
Volume increase	No
Type of structure	Off-site prefabricated ventilated façade system composed of vertical stainless-steel guidelines and connectors that allow to attach and bear loads of the cladding.
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation?	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process?	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	100
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	Ongoing
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Off-site prefabricated ventilated façade system composed of vertical stainless-steel guidelines and connectors that allow to attach and bear loads of the cladding. The cladding system is made of 1 mm thick painted aluminium cladding tiles. The thermal insulation is made of mineral wool attached to the system's vertical guidelines.
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Hanged to the existing facade.

Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/me- chanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	Air handling Unit located in a vertical position. The AHU incorporates two stages of heat recovery: the first is a passive heat exchanger (plate), and the second is an active heat exchanger with thermoelectric modules that provides supply air temperature control. The unit is connected to the interior space via supply and extract channels. The electric power for the thermoelectric modules is derived from the PVs or the grid.
Windows integrated in the panel?	No, windows replaced tra- ditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	-
Monitoring system?	-
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installa- tion (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-re- novation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee du- ration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Regenerar Barcelona

The latest modification of the Catalan Urban Planning Law (2022) allows the volumetric expansion of residential properties in exchange for implementing substantial improvements in their habitability, accessibility and water and energy efficiency. They are structures that add a new façade to buildings, allowing them to gain space through balconies, new rooms or community areas while improving their insulation and comfort. They also include installing solar panels, green roofs and rainwater harvesting systems on rooftops. December 2022 – March 2024: Manufacture and installation of the prototypes. April 2024- May 2025: Monitoring of the prototypes (to assess their impact on health and comfort, urban resilience, energy efficiency, circular economy and biodiversity). The project is presented as an open system that consists of a self-supporting wooden support - which is joined to the existing structure with anchors without transmitting loads - modular and dry assembled, capable of hosting diverse and adaptable forms of occupation and appropriation of space, different pre-existing situations and typologies and, in general, to diverse needs.

The prototype of the bioclimatic envelope is made up of the primary and secondary support structure plus the cistern kit, the vegetation and biodiversity kit, the photovoltaic kit, the volume expansion kit, the smart building kit and the community space kit. Gravent Hervent model recycled aluminum tilting windows that allow regulating air renewal without invading the space of the home. Recycled plastic planters with various elements of horizontal vegetation and climbing plants to cover the building, especially on the exterior of the façade. Didactic and informative screens in common outdoor and private indoor spaces with data visualization from the smart building kit.

General Data	
Address	Campus Diagonal-Besòs. Avinguda d'Eduard Maristany, 16 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs. Barcelona
Year of renovation	March 2024

Housing owner	BIT Habitat foundation. Barcelona City Council
General contractor	Research Group on Architectural Rehabilitation and Restoration (REARQ) from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC), GICITED (UPC), and CONSTRAULA
Panel manufacturer	Sorigue

Building information

Year of construction	N/A
Number of buildings	N/A
Number of floors (ground floor included)	N/A
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	N/A
Total living area (m2)	N/A
Facade surface (m2)	N/A
Roof surface (m2)	N/A
Type of structure	N/A
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	N/A

Retrofit Information

Internal renovation	N/A
Volume increase	Yes
Type of structure	It is a self-supporting wooden structure that adapts to the facade of the buildings to configure interior and exterior spaces. The vertical structure is made of solid Girona pine wood in the form of 2D frames, modular and dry assembled on site with machined joints. It is a structure of porches and a removable and dry-assembled wooden framework.
Scaffoldings	-
Inhabited during renovation?	N/A. It is a prototype
Tenant engagement process?	N/A
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	100%
New balconies?	Yes, discharged to the ground.

Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Exterior wooden facade slats mounted on wooden framework and thermal insulation, finished painted with photocatalytic paint.
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	On a removable and dry-assembled wooden framework,
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Insulation with 100% natural and ecological expanded cork conglomerate pressed in a closed autoclave.
Photovoltaic panels?	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	System of atomized cisterns on the roofs connected to a drip irrigation system and complemented by planters with incorporated cistern trays that allow rainwater to be collected, stored and used by the irrigation system, and channeled to a larger volume tank. on the ground floor.
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	187,500.00
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

StepUp Spanish pilot

StepUP project has developed affordable solutions and technologies aimed at transforming the energy renovation market and making the decarbonisation of existing buildings a reliable, attractive and sustainable investment. Renovation of the R&D facilities of the University of Navarra: Two test cells, small buildings each one with two floors using the P&P façade solution, incorporating P&P modules to address corner elements, and integrating third-party technologies.

StepUP Plug& Play envelope system: The plug-and-play façade system comprises customizable layers tailored to each project's requirements, emphasizing prefabrication for swift on-site assembly and minimal manual intervention. Developed by MANNI, specialists in steel-based products, the final design integrates metal-faced sandwich panels on a lightweight steel structure. Prefabricated off-site, these elements are installed as a single unit using a flexible anchoring system, allowing movement in three directions. The system's flexibility accommodates diverse existing building structures. Modular in design, the façade can be adjusted in dimensions. Its composition simplifies into seven main elements (Also seen in Figure 1) : (1) anchoring system, (2) galvanized steel structure, (3) insulated sandwich panels, (4) steel brackets, (5) aluminium profiles for cladding, (6) external cladding, and (7) flashing. Neither construction permits nor public grants were needed to do the renovation. The facility provided a good opportunity to renovate the test cells using the StepUP façade P&P solution and the time required to install the Plug and Play façade in a multi-storey building.

General Data	
Address	Pamplona
Year of renovation	2024
Housing owner	University of Navarra
General contractor	Construcciones ACR SAU
Panel manufacturer	Manni Group

Building information	
Year of construction	
Number of buildings	2
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	N/A
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	19.4 m2
Type of structure	
Facade surface (m2)	128 m ²
Roof surface (m2)	29 m ²
Type of structure	Brick layer façade
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	N/A
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Type of structure	5 regular modules per floor 4 square modules per floor 18P&P modules per test cell A total of 36P&P modules
Scaffoldings	Yes, just for a small part of the facade
Inhabited during renovation?	N/A
Tenant engagement process?	N/A
Total onsite works duration (days)	12
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	24

Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	<p>Ventilated high-pressure laminate (HPL) façade ultimately executed with concealed fixings.</p> <p>The renovation of each cell was accomplished through the installation of ten regular modules (five modules per floor) along with a total of eight corner modules (four per floor). This results in a total of 18 modules per test cell, covering an area of 64 m² of façade. Consequently, for the entire renovation of facilities, a total of 36 modules were installed, which included 20 regular modules and 16 corner modules. These modules together cover an area of 128 square meters, distributed across two 2-storey buildings.</p>
Panel weight handling (ex. hanged to the existing facade, new ground foundations)	Anchored to the existing facade
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	
Photovoltaic panels?	No
Solar thermal panels?	No
Systems (ex. pipes/cables/mechanical ventilation) integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	The integration of IT StepUP LEAN tools facilitated real-time monitoring of execution times, furnishing invaluable insights to assess the impact of on-site operations.
Windows integrated in the panel?	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system?	No
Total renovation cost (€)	N/A
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	N/A
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	

Lessons learnt (optional)	<p>First, it was completed the installation of the P&P modules in one test cell before proceeding with the installation of anchor elements in the other test cell. This approach allowed the team to apply lessons learned to improve efficiency and reduce complications during the second test cell's installation.</p> <p>Key findings underlined the need to improve the adaptability of corner modules and streamline panel fixing systems, thus minimizing on-site adjustments and optimizing installation efficiency.</p> <p>Anchor elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They did not have the correct measurement • There was not enough space in the anchor elements to insert the screws that hold the lower P&P module to the upper one. <p>Increase of the works on site:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sealing rubber of the P&P modules was not installed at Manni's facilities. They had to be installed on site. • The size of the screws used to anchor the substructure of the ventilated façade to the sandwich panel were too long. • The dimensions of the HPL panels are not correct. <p>Supply chain:</p> <p>The modules were ordered and assembled to be placed in columns. However, finally all those on the ground floor were placed first and then all those on the upper floor.</p>
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Henriëttedreef

The profound redevelopment of this 1960s social housing building demonstrates that Energiesprong is also applicable in large-scale and high-rise interventions. The compactness of the complex offers little space for the installation of photovoltaic systems for the generation of electricity; for this reason it was decided to integrate photovoltaic panels into the prefabricated facade modules, in addition to heating and ventilation systems, to maximize the generation surface. This approach overall made it possible to generate more energy than was used to operate the building and therefore return electricity to the grid.

The monitoring of performance and consumption went in parallel with workshops with the tenants to introduce them to the responsible and conscious use of the apartments, guiding them to understand and correctly use the consumption control tools. This process was fundamental for the satisfaction of the inhabitants and highlighted the importance of involvement and communication between those involved in the redevelopment.

General Data	
Address	Henriëttedreef, Utrecht
Year of renovation	2018 - 2021
Housing owner	Bo-Ex
General contractor	Bos Installatiewerken
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1960s
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (ground floor included)	10
Number of dwellings	58
Balconies?	Yes
Total living area (m ²)	-
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	-

"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	-
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	-
Inhabited during renovation	-
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies	-
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	-
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels	Yes
Solar thermal panels	-
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel	-
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, on the roof
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Hoog Lindoduin

The deep redevelopment of this 1960s social housing building demonstrates the potential for large-scale, sustainable renovation. The building stripped to its concrete shell, prefabricated and well-insulated timber-frame facades with durable ceramic cladding enhance energy performance and protect against coastal conditions. Wider pre-cast concrete galleries replace the previous deteriorating structures using anchors, ensuring durability without altering the original frame. Advanced systems, including individual heat pumps connected to a geothermal source and CO₂-controlled ventilation with heat recovery, significantly reduce energy demand. Resident training sessions introduced the proper use of these systems, fostering sustainable living practices.

A combination of modern prefabrication and traditional craftsmanship ensures a seamless fit - despite the building's mid-century construction variability - and achieved a comprehensive upgrade, improving energy efficiency, living comfort, and aesthetic quality.

General Data	
Address	Westduinweg Scheveningen
Year of renovation	2018-2021
Housing owner	Woningcorporatie Vestia
General contractor	BAM Wonen
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1963
Number of buildings	1
Number of floors (groundfloor included)	14
Number of dwellings	182
Balconies?	Walkways
Total living area (m ²)	Around 60/home
Facade surface (m ²)	
Roof surface (m ²)	
Type of structure	Beton structure / timber frame façade

Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	Label F

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	(only the balconies)
Scaffoldings	None
Inhabited during renovation	No, move out for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies	Yes, demolished and hanged to new facade
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Rc-panels > 4.5 K.m ² /W
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	Yes, timber frame façade
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Yes, each apartment has its individual heatpump connected to a ground source (for heating and cooling)
Monitoring system	-
Total renovation cost (€)	Around 200,000/home
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Nieuw Buinen

The project includes the in-depth redevelopment of three residential buildings from the 1970s and concerns a very common cluster and therefore has a high potential for replicability and scalability.

Using prefabricated and pre-finished elements of facades and roofing with integrated fixtures and systems and having previously prepared the anchoring and preliminary works, the complete intervention was carried out in just one day of construction for each house. All the components of the systems have been integrated into a new element, a vertical column integrated into the external facades; this allows for any maintenance without inconvenience for residents and repairs even without their presence. A new heat pump generates energy for heating and domestic hot water, powered by a photovoltaic system that occupies the entire roof.

The intervention therefore made it possible to reach the Net Zero standard, which was guaranteed for 30 years.

General Data	
Address	Nieuw Buinen
Year of renovation	2016
Housing owner	Lefier
General contractor	Rottinghuis / VolkerWessels
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1960s
Number of buildings	5
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	30
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	-
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	-
"Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)"	-
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	-
Volume increase	Yes
Scaffoldings	No
Inhabited during renovation	-
Tenant engagement process	-
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies	-
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	-
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels	-
Solar thermal panels	-
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel	-
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	-
Monitoring system	-
Total renovation cost (€)	100 000 per home
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Woningen Molenbuurt

The project involved the in-depth retrofit of 52 homes, demonstrating high-potential for replicability and scalability of the efficient and low-disturbance building upgrades.

The buildings were entirely enclosed with a highly-insulated envelope, using prefabricated panels for the façade and roof, improving energy efficiency and thermal performance. The panels also integrated photovoltaic and solar thermal panels and a mechanical ventilation system. The renovation was carried out with minimal disruption to the residents, who remained in their homes throughout the entire 150-day process. No relocation was necessary.

Resident engagement support the transition to sustainable living, demonstrating a holistic approach to energy efficiency and community integration.

General Data	
Address	Molenwijk
Year of renovation	2021/2022
Housing owner	Woningstichting Plavei
General contractor	Klumps
Panel manufacturer	Rc-panels

Building information	
Year of construction	1967
Number of buildings	52
Number of floors (groundfloor included)	3
Number of dwellings	52
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	125
Facade surface (m2)	77
Roof surface (m2)	84
Type of structure	Beton / tunnelbekisting
Energy generation pre-renovation (type/fuel + centralized or autonomous)	Gas
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	Label F

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	150
% facade renovated offsite	100%
% roof renovated offsite	100%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	84
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Rc-panels > https://www.rcpanels.nl/
Panel weight handling	?
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	No
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, integrated in the roof/facade
Solar thermal panels	Yes, integrated in the roof/facade
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	MV-systeem, type D
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	No
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	4700000
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	43000
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	40
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	25%
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Nottingham

The pilot project involved 10 homes in the city's housing association, the first in the UK to join Energiesprong. The buildings were particularly inefficient, with particularly cold conditions in winter and lighting problems. The solution was contracted at a pre-established cost, which considered the entire lifetime cost of the building. Tenants were involved in developing the design brief, meaning the solution provider was able to include small additional elements that made a big difference to tenants' lives. The wall panels arrived prefabricated complete with insulation, double glazed windows and a durable panel finish, ready to be craned into place. Tenants were able to remain in the residence throughout the renovation, which was completed in one week.

The project achieved significant productivity improvements compared to traditional, reducing installation time by 60% and costs by 45%.

General Data	
Address	Keswick Close, Nottingham
Year of renovation	2022
Housing owner	Nottingham City Homes
General contractor	Melius Homes
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1960's
Number of buildings	18 terraced houses, 13 terraced bungalows, 12 terraced flats
Number of floors (ground floor included)	3
Number of dwellings	43
Balconies	No
Total living area (m ²)	102
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	Crosswall House (Non-traditional)
Energy generation pre-renovation	Individual gas boiler
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	Yes
Volume increase	Yes
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure	Factory produced timber and mineral wool facades with weather boarding, factory fitted windows, doors and flashing
Panel weight handling	
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, integrated in the roof/facade
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel	Yes
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Air source heat pumps
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Sutton, London (Coulsdon 5)

The first phase of the Energiesprong Sutton program allowed the redevelopment of 5 terraced buildings from the 1940s originally built with non-insulated walls and therefore with poor energy and comfort performance. The retrofit intervention made it possible, using prefabricated elements, to reach Net Zero energy standards, creating more high-performance and desirable homes. Technical solutions were used such as insulated facade panels, a photovoltaic system on the roof, high-performance windows and doors and a heat pump generator. The redevelopment project has a high potential for replicability: the next phase will involve 100 homes, with over 1900 suitable for equivalent redevelopment in the neighbourhood.

An effective process of involving the inhabitants was implemented, concluded with the monitoring of the inhabitants' satisfaction which highlighted very positive results.

General Data	
Address	31 Longlands Avenue, Coulsdon, CR52QG
Year of renovation	2021
Housing owner	Sutton Housing Partnership
General contractor	Equans
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1950s
Number of buildings	5
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	5
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m2)	83
Facade surface (m2)	-
Roof surface (m2)	-
Type of structure	Unity house (Non-traditional)
Energy generation pre-renovation	Individual gas boiler
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m2)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	-
% roof renovated offsite	-
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m2/day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wetherby External Wall Insulation system
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, integrated in the roof/facade
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	-
Windows integrated in the panel?	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Air source heat pumps
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m2)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m2)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO2eq/m2 or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	-
Performance guarantee duration	-
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

Sutton, London (St Helier)

Bow Tie Construction were selected by Energiesprong UK and Sutton Housing Partnership to deliver an Ofgem Eco funded deep retrofit of a terrace of four and a terrace of two houses. Bow Tie's designers were responsible for all design elements and construction was undertaken by Bow Tie's builders. The residents received the retrofit at no cost to themselves.

The project had to be delivered within a guaranteed maximum price per unit and would target an annual space heating performance of 50 kwh/m²/annum with an airtightness of 1 air change per hour. The houses would be taken off gas. All heating and hot water would be provided by the Ventive compact unit comprising exhaust air heat pump, MVHR and thermal store. Electricity from the PV panels would first go to the Ventive unit to charge the thermal store, then be used by the house, any surplus would be exported to the grid with residents receiving the benefit.

General Data	
Address	476 Middleton Road
Year of renovation	2023
Housing owner	Sutton Housing Partnership
General contractor	Osborne and Bowtie
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	-
Number of buildings	10
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	10
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m ²)	64-67
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	Cavity Wall
Energy generation pre-renovation	Individual gas boiler

Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m²)

-

Retrofit Information

Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	0%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies?	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	Wetherby External Wall Insulation system
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, integrated in the roof/ facade
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Monodraught integrated energy module in porch
Monitoring system?	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	-
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	10 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	Improved monitoring on Monodraught Home Zero pod required

Enfield, London

Edmonton residents are set to benefit from a scheme that will make their homes more energy efficient after Enfield Council was awarded government cash. The council has begun ‘retrofit’ improvement works to boost energy efficiency at ten domestic properties in Edmonton Green and Haselbury wards, making them easier to heat and keep warm and replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy sources. The works are part of a three-year partnership alongside seven other councils in London and are set to deliver more than 250 housing retrofits in total.

The Dutch ‘Energiesprong’ model will be used to make each property included in the scheme zero-carbon. This includes adding double-glazed windows and high-performance doors, rooftop solar panels to generate electricity, efficient heating and ventilation systems and external insulation. The council was awarded almost £600,000 of government funding to enable the retrofit works. Deputy leader Ergin Erbil said: “Enfield Council has a strong track record in leading carbon reduction and innovative energy projects.

General Data	
Address	167 Haselbury Road, London, N9 9BN
Year of renovation	2022/23
Housing owner	London Borough of Enfield
General contractor	Osborne Property Services
Panel manufacturer	-

Building information	
Year of construction	1930s
Number of buildings	10
Number of floors (ground floor included)	2
Number of dwellings	10
Balconies?	No
Total living area (m ²)	81.92
Facade surface (m ²)	-
Roof surface (m ²)	-
Type of structure	Traditional house

Energy generation pre-renovation	Individual gas boiler
Energy consumption pre-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-

Retrofit Information	
Internal renovation	No
Volume increase	No
Scaffoldings	Yes, for the majority of the facade
Inhabited during renovation	Yes, inhabited for the total works duration
Tenant engagement process	Yes
Total onsite works duration (days)	-
% facade renovated offsite	0%
% roof renovated offsite	0%
New balconies	No, building has no balconies
Facade installation time (m ² /day)	-
Panel structure (material + dimension + other info)	-
Panel weight handling	-
Circular/ biobased materials? If yes what type	-
Photovoltaic panels	Yes, installed after the panels
Solar thermal panels	No
Systems integrated in the panel? If yes, what type	No
Windows integrated in the panel	No, windows replaced traditionally
Heat pump? If yes, where has it been installed	Air source, rear garden
Monitoring system	Yes
Total renovation cost (€)	£1,562,776
Facade cost, supply + installation (€/m ²)	-
Energy consumption post-renovation (kwh/m ²)	-
% consumption covered by renewables (PV/ ST panels)	-
LCA, if any (tCO ₂ eq/m ² or other KPIs)	-
Antiseismic improvement	No
Performance guarantee duration	10 years
Lessons learnt (optional)	-

4.1 Emerging technological trends

Introduction

As illustrated across the various case studies, several EU countries have already initiated offsite renovation programmes, adopting a wide spectrum of solutions that range from partially industrialized approaches to fully prefabricated façade systems. The diversity of these initiatives reflects the heterogeneity of local building stocks, climatic conditions, regulatory frameworks, and market readiness, all of which shape the technological choices and implementation strategies in each context.

To enrich the second edition of the Outlook, a trend analysis has been included to begin mapping the evolution and market uptake of offsite façade panels in Europe. This additional layer helps to iden-

tify emerging patterns, assess levels of maturity across different national markets, and highlight how different technological pathways are being developed to respond to varying performance requirements, cost constraints, and labour availability.

This chapter provides an analysis of the market and a comparative benchmark through the cataloguing of various construction technologies across Europe (primarily Germany, France, and Italy). The data evaluates offsite retrofit solutions—ranging various materials from concrete to steel, timber, sandwich on steel anchoring and straw—based on technical parameters and market maturity.

Methodology

To be able to assess trends and draw meaningful conclusions, different data has been gathered:

- Structure material as main differentiating parameter, see Image X
- Type of solution such as panel, frame or others;
- Country of the company developing and producing the solution;
- Performance, only thermal or also anti-seismic;
- Installation speed in m² per day;
- Weight of the solution in kg per m²;
- Panels max height and width in meters;
- Year of the launch of the solution in the market;
- Number of residential units and buildings retrofitted with the solutions;
- Development phase between Concept, Mock-up, Pilot project, <100 Retrofitted units, 100<500 Retrofitted units, >500 Retrofitted units, ND;
- Use trend between Never pilot tested, Pilot tested but not replicated, Replicated, Market competitive;
- Outlook between Positive (retrofit with solution replicated within 1 year), Stable (retrofit with solution replicated within 1-3 years), Negative (retrofit with solution not replicated within 3 years).

The cost of façade panels has not been included in the analysis, as it is difficult to parameterize and often unclear which components are covered within reported prices. Moreover, panel costs alone are not representative of the overall investment required for a full building scale retrofit intervention, which typically includes design work, site preparation, logistics, installation, integration with building services, and finishing works. For a detailed discussion of economic considerations and the underlying business model, please refer to Chapter XX.

To gather the required data and be able to extract meaningful market readiness assessments, different entities have been contacted from 8 European Countries: Austria (Renowave), Belgium (Buildwise), France (Ressorts), Germany (Depact), Italy (EDERA), Slovenia (Institute for Innovation and Development of University of Ljubljana), Spain (Polytechnic University of Valencia) and United Kingdom (Energiesprong UK). Overall, data for 74 offsite retrofit solutions, with different level of completeness, were collected providing an interesting perspective on trends at national (for some Countries) and European level.

Renders of the different structure materials of offsite façade panels

Timber structure
@woodbeton

Steel structure
@Manni Greentech

sandwich on steel anchoring structure
@Isopan

Concrete structure
@structurama

Straw structure
@Ricehouse

Trend analysis

Considering all the solutions gathered, at European level:

- Market is clearly more mature for timber structure solutions, with 68% of the whole dataset; steel structure is in second, with 18%; sandwich on steel anchoring structure in third, with 7%; residuals are concrete and straw structure, with respectively 4% and 3%. This is a consequence of the most mature markets and technological trends, as Germany and France have a strong tradition in timber construction and as it is perceived as more sustainable than other options.

- Almost half of the solution taken into consideration with available data (47%) have been applied to real projects: in detail, 30% are market competitive and therefore with large utilization potential, and roughly 12% have been tested and replicated, while 36% have not been replicated, underlining the problem of a necessary balance between technical performance and overall costs to provide real advantages for users.
- The large number of solutions never pilot tested, 21%, testifies the ongoing research & development efforts of many companies in the Industrialized Renovation sector.

- Is as well clear that the test pilot phase is a recommended and necessary step for technical, legal and economical validation of the solution, as simulations are not enough without a hands-on approach. 11% have no data available, so have not been included in the previous considerations.

- Overall market outlook is healthy, with more than two thirds, in detail 70%, of the solutions with positive (39%) or stable (31%) score. Considering the long times of the construction industry, especially with respect to innovation, the current replication trend within three years gives optimistic views towards the market future development.

There is a correlation between technology, weight, installation speed and dimensions, taking into consideration only timber and steel solutions, for the availability of data.

Timber frame structure solutions, due to the significant thickness of vertical and horizontal structural mullions, tend to be used for bigger and heavier panels (71 kg/m² on average), with limitations due to transportation, and therefore corresponding to one floor (3.2 meters on average) in height and one or half truck trailer (6 or 12 meters on average) in length. Bigger panels have as consequence that on site in-

stallation of prefabricated façade elements is faster, with a speed of 180 m²/day on average.

Light steel frame solutions, on the contrary, due to the thin structural mullions that gather strengths by the C shape profile rather than by the overall thickness, tend to be used for smaller and lighter panels (56 kg/m² on average), corresponding to one floor (3.2 meters on average) in height and half truck trailer (6 meters on average) in length, despite the possibility of a full truck trailer if needed. Smaller panels have as consequence that on site installation of prefabricated façade elements is slower, with a speed of 134 m²/day on average.

This analysis does not consider off site factory production time, providing only a partial prove of improved productivity compared to traditional renovations.

- With 20 solutions considered and analyzed, the French offsite retrofit market seems to be the most mature in Europe within the Countries considered. The focus is on timber structure materials, with 16 solutions, and 4 solutions in steel. The use trend shows 5 solutions to be market competitive, with significant number of units renovated; of these 3 are steel and 2 timber structures. 6 solutions have been replicated and 8 tested, all with timber structure;

only 1, in steel, has not been pilot tested. The outlook is positive for 13 solutions, so retrofit with solution replicated within one year and it is stable for 6 ones, so retrofit with solution replicated within three years; these data describe a market in evolution and good growth potential.

- With 16 solutions considered and analyzed, the German market is well directed and evolving quickly. The focus is on timber structure materials, with 13 solutions; other materials such as steel and sandwich on steel anchoring have 2 and 1 respectively.

The use trend seems to be very positive, with 9 solutions that are market competitive, all with timber structure, and the other 7 pilot tested but not replicated. The outlook is positive for 9 solutions and stable for 7 ones. These data represent a market focused mostly on one structure material with good development potential.

- With 19 solutions considered and analyzed, the Italian market seems to be very active in the research and development. All technologies and structure materials solutions are being considered, with focus mostly on timber and steel (7 and 6 solutions respectively); In addition, there are 3 sandwich on steel anchoring panels, while concrete and straw panels, with 2 and 1 solutions respectively, attract less interest and is less mature. In particular, concrete panels and heavier structures might be relevant for the Italian market due to their anti-seismic performance required in some areas. The use trend shows that only 1 solution is market competitive, in sandwich on steel anchoring with significant number of units renovated, and 1 have been replicated, with timber structure; 4 have been pilot tested but not replicated, all with timber structure, while the others have never pilot tested, symptom of a growing interest for the offsite retrofit market with results awaited in the next years. The outlook underlines, consistently with use trends, only 2 positive solutions.

4. Case studies

No further considerations were conducted for the remaining Countries, due to the lack of complete data or the insufficient statistical sample. 8 solutions were considered from Austria, all with timber structure; 2 from Belgium still in timber structure (they both have a stable market active also in the Netherlands but 1 is recently closing its business); 3 from Slovenia (all in timber and in pilot test phase only), 4 from Spain, with concrete, timber, sandwich on steel and straw structures; and 2 from the United Kingdom, with steel and timber structures. These numbers do not directly imply that the market is less structured in these Countries. Indeed, the fact that no homogeneous collections of data has been made is partially linked to the lack of a dedicated team focused on offsite retrofit development, such as Energiesprong in French, Italy and Germany.

Conclusion

The analysis confirms that the European market for offsite retrofit solutions is still in an early stage of development, yet it already shows promising signs of technological innovation, increasing maturity, and cross-country learning. With most of the solutions being less than five years old, the sector is evolving rapidly, driven by advances in industrialized construction, digital design, and the growing demand for high-performance, low-disruption renovation methods.

Despite this progress, the gap between current deployment levels and the scale of renovation required across Europe remains significant. To reach climate neutrality and meet the EU's energy-efficiency targets, millions of existing residential units will need to be upgraded within the next decade. Achieving this level of transformation will require renovation methods that are not only technically reliable but also fast, cost-effective, and replicable at industrial scale.

Offsite retrofit solutions—particularly panelised façade systems—have the potential to play a central role in closing this gap. Their ability to reduce on-site construction time, improve quality control, and integrate multiple performance layers into a single prefabricated element makes them well-suited for large-scale deployment. However, for these solutions to reach their full potential, several conditions must be strengthened: continued R&D and pilot testing, improved cost competitiveness, more mature value chains, and supportive regulatory environments that recognise and incentivise industrialised renovation. As European countries advance at different speeds and follow diverse technological pathways, understanding these variations and the emerging pattern across national markets becomes essential for accelerating market uptake. Indeed, if Europe is to renovate millions of buildings within the timeframe required, offsite solutions will need to move from promising innovations to mainstream practice. This transition represents both a necessity and an opportunity: a chance to reshape the construction sector, reduce environmental impact, and deliver better, healthier homes at the pace that the energy transition demands.

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